

Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C: A list of critiques by Harri Hemilä

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The scientific literature on vitamin C contains a remarkable amount of poor-quality analysis and misleading reporting.

Several randomized trials have been analyzed incorrectly or reported in a misleading manner (#5, #6, #19, #25, #35, #38, #45, #49, #53, #60, #62, #67, #68, #71, #76, #77, #78, #79, #89, #91, #96). For example, the subgroup analysis in the Karlowski (1975) trial was based on participants' guesses regarding treatment allocation; however, the trial report did not disclose that 42% of participants were excluded from this analysis (#5, #6, #16). It is unfortunate that on the basis of the erroneous analysis of that trial, vitamin C for the common cold has been frequently used as an example of the "placebo-effect in action" (e.g. #5, #10, #11, #12, #13, #19, #22, #27, #28, #33, #34, #41, #75, #86, 95). Three trials involving critically ill patients administered vitamin C for only 4 days, however the investigators failed to consider the significant increases in mortality occurring immediately after the abrupt discontinuation of treatment (#62, #89, #90, #94).

Numerous systematic reviews and meta-analyses have been affected by inappropriate trial inclusion, errors in data extraction, and flawed analytical methods (#4, #7, #14, #15, #16, #17, #30, #35, #39, #40, #46, #48, #50, #51, #52, #53, #54, #55, #56, #57, #58, #59, #61, #63, #65, #69, #72, #73, #74, #88, #90, #92, #94, #97); notably, three of these erroneous meta-analyses were published as Cochrane reviews (#30, #40, #58, #59, #65). In the most influential meta-analysis, Thomas Chalmers (1975) calculated that vitamin C reduced the duration of the common cold by only 0.11 days. Subsequent correction of the errors in 1995 increased the estimated effect to 0.93 days (#4). Despite being flawed, the 1975 review unfortunately continues to be cited, perpetuating a substantially underestimated assessment of vitamin C's efficacy.

One of the central goals of contemporary biomedical research is to identify specific causes and effects. The strength of randomized controlled trials lies in the ability to attribute observed differences between study groups specifically to the intervention under investigation. Nevertheless, several analyses included trials in which vitamin C was administered together with other substances (#54, #56, #57, #63, #88, #90, #94), thereby confounding interpretation because observed effects—or the absence of them—could not be attributed exclusively to vitamin C.

The seriousness of these concerns is reflected by the fact that four vitamin C papers were subsequently retracted (#38, #53, #74) and one Cochrane review was formally withdrawn (#40).

The critiques listed below were written by Harri Hemilä for two reasons: partly to document problems in specific publications, but primarily, to caution researchers against uncritically accepting studies when looking at evaluations of vitamin C research.

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<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/?term=hemila+h>

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

100. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Are the UK's vitamin C recommendations evidence-based? A critical comment.**

Br J Nutr. 2026;135(4):381-6.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/41424103>

<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0007114525105941>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC12929015>

This critique challenges the justification for the 40 mg/day vitamin C recommendation in the UK.

Regular font indicates new comments in this list

we argue that the UK recommendation overlooked key evidence available at the time.

Specifically, at least six controlled trials published before 1991 reported benefits from

vitamin C supplementation in participants whose baseline vitamin C intake was already 40 mg/d or higher.

Italics indicate extracts of the critique

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1961974>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13946536>

<https://archive.org/details/b32220546/page/116/mode/2up>

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/pguqct9n/items?canvas=145>

<https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5bab98f7ed915d2bb2f56367/>

[Dietary Reference Values for Food Energy and Nutrients for the United Kingdom 1991 .pdf](#)

Dietary reference values for food energy and nutrients for the United Kingdom.

Report of the Panel on Dietary Reference Values of the Committee on Medical Aspects of Food Policy.

Rep Health Soc Subj (Lond). 1991; p.117-122.

At the end of the record, there are links and the citation of the focus of the critique

99. Hemilä H. **Erroneous references in the commentary by Wang et al. (2024).**

PubPeer 2026 April.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20304333>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/B5B4ABD9FB9231132CE6B67A09E5A4#1>

Wang et al. [1] write that “Hu et al.[2] performed a meta-analysis with trial sequential analysis of randomized controlled trials on patients undergoing heart surgery who received vitamin C.”

However, the Hu et al. paper was shown to be flawed [3]. For example, “Hu et al. stated in their methods that ‘studies that met the following criteria were included: randomized controlled trials (RCTs) of adult patients who underwent cardiac surgery; patients randomly assigned to receive vitamin C or placebo ... Any studies of non-randomized designs ... were excluded’. However, Hu included the study by Carnes et al. although that was not an RCT” [3] and “In their Fig. 4, Hu et al. stated that the standard deviation (SD) of the mean duration of ICU stay in the vitamin C group was 24.9 hours in the trial by Colby et al. However, Colby reported in their Table 1 and text that the SD for the duration of ICU stay was 249.9 hours in their vitamin C group, i.e. 10 times greater than Hu claimed” [3].

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38445473>

Wang C, Sun Z, Zhou W. A commentary on ‘Efficacy and safety of vitamin C for atrial fibrillation after cardiac surgery: a meta-analysis with trial sequential analysis of randomized controlled trials’.

Int J Surg. 2024 Jul 1;110(7):4416-4417.

98. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Vitamin C in infectious diseases: Misrepresentation of the evidence.**

Nutrition. 2025;139:112889.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/40716992>

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nut.2025.112889>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/393285984>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/601620>

... For these and other reasons not detailed here, we consider that Li's review misrepresents the existing evidence and misleads readers about the potential effects of vitamin C on infections.

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/40154019>

Li R, Guan L, Liu Y, Hu Z, Liu J, Li C, Min H. The roles of vitamin C in infectious diseases: A comprehensive review. *Nutrition*. 2025

97. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Errors in a meta-analysis on vitamin C and COVID-19.**

Nutr Rev. 2025;83(7):1378-9.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/40238205>

<https://doi.org/10.1093/nutrit/nuaf044>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/603484>

For example,

... a relevant large randomized study was published in October 2023 ... but was not included in the analysis... For these and many other reasons, we consider that this meta-analysis is misleading.

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/39527016>

Qin M, Xu K, Chen Z, Wen X, Tang Y, Gao Y, Zhang H, Ma X. Effects of vitamin C supplements on clinical outcomes and hospitalization duration for patients with coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Nutr Rev*. 2025

96. Hemilä, H. **Effect of vitamin C deprivation on the duration of colds in the Sheffield study (1953): A statistical analysis.** Zenodo 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14717360>

The finding that vitamin C deprivation prolonged the duration of colds was not reported in the trial summaries published in the Lancet (1948) or the Proceedings of the Nutrition Society (1953). Moreover, this effect on cold duration is absent from the current UK recommendations for vitamin C. As a consequence, the findings related to the common cold from the Sheffield trial have been largely overlooked and underreported for decades.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/13119061>

Vitamin C requirement of human adults. *Spec Rep Ser Med Res Counc (GB)*. 1953

95. Hemilä H. **Blinding: Misleading interpretation of the Karlowski (1975) trial in the Consort (2025) statement.** *BMJ Rapid Response* 2025 June 11.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20308865>

<https://www.bmj.com/content/389/bmj-2024-081124/rr>

The CONSORT (2025) statement [1] writes about blinding as follows:

“Unblinded outcome assessors may differentially assess subjective outcomes, and unblinded data analysts may introduce bias through the choice of analytical strategies, such as the selection of favourable time points or outcomes and by decisions to remove patients from the analyses. These biases have been well documented,” p.27 in [1].

*One of the references to this statement, ref. no. 328, is to **the trial by Karlowski, Chalmers et al. (1975) [2]**. In the randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial, Thomas Karlowski, Thomas Chalmers et al. observed that 6 g/day vitamin C significantly shortened the duration of colds, yet they concluded “that the effects demonstrated might be explained equally well by a break in the double blind.”*

*The **Karlowski (1975) trial** has been widely used as evidence for the existence of the placebo effect, and also as evidence that the observed effects of vitamin C on the common cold are explained by the placebo effect [3]. However, it was shown already in 1996 that the placebo-effect interpretation of Karlowski, Chalmers, et al. was not valid [4-6]...*

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/40228832>

Hopewell S, Chan AW, Collins GS, Hróbjartsson A, Moher D, Schulz KF, Tunn R, Aggarwal R, Berkwits M, Berlin JA, Bhandari N, Butcher NJ, Campbell MK, Chidebe RCW, Elbourne D, Farmer A, Fergusson

DA, Golub RM, Goodman SN, Hoffmann TC, Ioannidis JPA, Kahan BC, Knowles RL, Lamb SE, Lewis S, Loder E, Offringa M, Ravaud P, Richards DP, Rockhold FW, Schriger DL, Siegfried NL, Staniszevska S, Taylor RS, Thabane L, Torgerson D, Vohra S, White IR, Boutron I.
CONSORT 2025 explanation and elaboration: updated guideline for reporting randomised trials.
BMJ. 2025 Apr 14;389:e081124.

94. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Vitamin C for patients with sepsis?** Front Med. 2024;11:1450091.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/39364019>

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2024.1450091>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11446763>

The intensive care medicine rapid practice guideline panel recently published a clinical practice guideline on the use of vitamin C for adult patients with sepsis. The panel recommended against its use. However, there are several factors which the panel seems not to have considered...

Specificity is important when looking at evidence for any intervention. If we want to determine whether vitamin C has an effect on sepsis, the comparison should be between vitamin C and a control, and not between vitamin C combined with other substances and a control (2). The panel considered that their most informative analysis was in their Supplementary Figure S1, but four of the six included trials administered vitamin C with other substances (1)...

The panel “had more confidence in estimates of mortality at 90 days than at shorter time periods” though they were puzzled by “the potential difference between estimates of short- and long-term mortality”. However, the 90-day follow-up is misguided...

There are numerous recent reports of patients suffering from scurvy and several of them were in the ICU (5, 10–20). Scurvy can cause dyspnea, edema, chest pain, and other pains, whereas gum pathology is not always present (5, 11). We are concerned that the ICM-RPG panel guideline may discourage the use of vitamin C for critically ill patients on the basis of statistically unsound analyses.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37500083>

Reintam Blaser A, et al. Intravenous vitamin C therapy in adult patients with sepsis: A rapid practice guideline. Acta Anaesthesiol Scand. 2023

93. Hemilä H. **Misleading statements about vitamin C and the common cold in article on treatments for common cold in children by Gill et al. (2024).** BMJ Rapid Response, 2024 January 25.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20305129>

<https://www.bmj.com/content/384/bmj-2023-075306/rr-0>

Gill et al. reviewed common cold treatments for children [1]. In Table 2 they refer to our Cochrane review on vitamin C and the common cold [2] and state the summary of evidence as “No consistent effect [of vitamin C] on the duration or severity of colds”. The topic is not discussed any further in the text section.

In fact, in our Cochrane review we calculated that in placebo-controlled trials, regular >0.2 g/day vitamin C shortened the duration of colds in children by 14.2% (7.3 to 21%; P = 0.00005); Analysis 2.1.2 (Trials with children) [2]. Furthermore, our calculation is based on 14 comparisons, whereas Gill states in their table that the number of vitamin C studies in our review on was 7. Thus, in contrast to Gill’s statement, our meta-analysis found that there is a consistent beneficial effect of regular vitamin C administration on common cold duration in children...

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38272497>

Gill PJ, Onakpoya IJ, Buchanan F, Birnie KA, Van den Bruel A.

Treatments for cough and common cold in children. BMJ. 2024 Jan 25;384:e075306.

92. Hemilä H. **Several shortcomings in the meta-analysis on vitamin C and COVID-19**

by Xu et al (2024). PubPeer 2025 June.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20157484>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/F13FE45BA20BA045B484B3B3F89571#1>

For example,

Xu et al. [1] published a meta-analysis aiming to analyze the effect of vitamin C on outcomes for patients with COVID-19...

Figure 2A [1] provides very strong evidence that the trials are not estimating a single, common effect, as indicated by a highly significant test for heterogeneity ($P < 0.0001$). Given this strong evidence of heterogeneity, the average effect is meaningless...

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/39421622>

Xu W, Wang P, Wan J, Tan Y, Liu Y, Chen Q, Zheng Y, Yu X, Fan S, Jorge Luis CD, Zhang Y.

Effect of vitamin C supplementation on outcomes in patients with COVID-19: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Front Nutr.* 2024 Oct 3;11:1465670.

91. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Rebound effect explains the divergence in survival after 5 days in a controlled trial on vitamin C for COVID-19 patients.** *Front Med.* 2024;11:1391346.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38841576>

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2024.1391346>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11151746>

Adhikari et al. did not justify the choice of 4-day vitamin C administration...

Although Adhikari et al. studied COVID-19 patients, they did not refer to the COVID A to Z trial [see #71], which found a 70% increase in the recovery rate of outpatient cases of COVID-19 patients when administering 8 g/day vitamin C for 10 days...

Given the published number of patients remaining at day 15 [vitamin C 763; control 414], we calculated that between days 5 and 15, there were 176 deaths in the vitamin C group and 67 deaths in the control group. These data indicate that in the time range from 5 to 15 days, those in the vitamin C group had 1.35 times the risk of dying than those in the control group (RR = 1.35; 95% CI 1.04–1.74; $P = 0.026$). This increased mortality occurred directly after the termination of the 4-day intravenous vitamin C.

the Adhikari et al. (17) trial should not be considered as a counterargument to giving vitamin C to COVID-19 patients. Instead, all three trials that terminated 4-day vitamin C administration abruptly, provide evidence that vitamin C should not be abruptly stopped if the patients are still critically ill.

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37877585>

Adhikari NKJ, Hashmi M, Tirupakuzhi Vijayaraghavan BK, Haniffa R, Beane A, Webb SA, Angus DC, Gordon AC, Cook DJ, Guyatt GH, Berry LR, Lorenzi E, Mouncey PR, Au C, Pinto R, Ménard J, et al.

Intravenous Vitamin C for Patients Hospitalized With COVID-19: Two Harmonized Randomized Clinical Trials. *JAMA.* 2023 Nov 14;330(18):1745-1759.

90. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Concerns with the revised Japanese recommendation for administering vitamin C to septic patients.** *J Intensive Care.* 2023;11(1):52.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37957677>

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40560-023-00702-2>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10641959>

... They carried out a new literature search and identified 12 new RCTs, performing a revised meta-analysis of 23 RCTs in all and reversing the 2020 recommendation. However, 13 of the 23 listed trials administered combinations of antioxidants and other drugs, such as hydrocortisone and thiamine. If the scientific question is about the specific effect of vitamin C on sepsis, then the included trials should only examine vitamin C. For example, a recent observational study indicated significantly different effects from vitamin C alone and from vitamin C together with hydrocortisone...

there is no justification to firmly recommend “against administering vitamin C to septic patients”. That conclusion was based on 23 trials, half of which did not administer vitamin C alone. Therefore, the revised meta-analysis is not valid as to the specific effects of vitamin C.

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36447298>

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40560-022-00641-4>

Guideline committee of The Japanese Clinical Practice Guidelines for Management of Sepsis and Septic Shock 2020; Japanese Society of Intensive Care Medicine; Japanese Association for Acute Medicine.

The revised recommendation for administering vitamin C in septic patients: the Japanese Clinical Practice Guidelines for Management of Sepsis and Septic Shock 2020. *J Intensive Care*. 2022

89. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Abrupt termination of vitamin C from ICU patients may increase mortality: Secondary analysis of the LOVIT trial.** *Eur J Clin Nutr*. 2023;77(4):490-4.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36539454>

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41430-022-01254-8>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10115628>

The increased mortality in the vitamin C group in the LOVIT trial is not explained by ongoing vitamin C administration, but by the abrupt termination of vitamin C. The LOVIT trial findings should not be interpreted as evidence against vitamin C therapy for critically ill patients.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35704292>

Lamontagne F, Masse MH, Menard J, Sprague S, Pinto R, Heyland DK, Cook DJ, Battista MC, et al. Intravenous Vitamin C in Adults with Sepsis in the Intensive Care Unit. *N Engl J Med*. 2022 Jun 23;386(25):2387-2398.

88. Hemilä H. **Erroneous data in a meta-analysis on vitamin C and the common cold by Saeed (2023).** PubPeer 2023 September.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19893106>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/447CAC9813A0D535D018047143870A#1>

For example,

On the first line of Figure 2, Saeed states that the mean number of colds in the Coulehan (1974) trial was 19 in the vitamin C group (N = 190) and 23 in the placebo group (N = 192). However, these are not the mean numbers of colds, but they are the total number of colds in the group. The correct means are 0.1 (= 19/190) and 0.12 (= 23/192)...

On the third line of Figure 2, Saeed gives incorrect SD valued for the Bancalari (1984) trial...

The fourth line of Figure 2 gives data for the Cohen (2004) trial. However, the Cohen trial is not a vitamin C trial, as participants were administered also Echinacea and propofol.

The fifth line of Figure 2 gives is data for the Garaiova (2021) trial. However, the Garaiova trial is not a vitamin C trial, as participants were administered also probiotics.

If the scientific question is, whether vitamin C has effects on the common cold, then the included trials should be limited to trials in which the only difference between the trial groups is vitamin C...

<https://doi.org/10.26689/jcnr.v7i1.4403>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/366909468>

Saeed H, Abdelrahim MEA. A meta-analysis of the effectiveness of vitamin C in the prevention and treatment of childhood upper respiratory tract infections.

Journal of Clinical and Nursing Research 2023

87. Hemilä H. **Misleading findings in Dresen’s review (2023) on vitamin C for critical illness.** PubPeer 2023 March.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19861833>
<https://pubpeer.com/publications/2C4D925EB3E88C3305E7DED31D2F53#1>
 A number of erroneous statements, and references to papers that had been demonstrated false several years before Dresen’s paper. For example,
Dresen’s reference 59 also has a number of errors [59a]. For example, in their Fig. 4, Hu et al stated [59] that the standard deviation (SD) of the mean duration of ICU stay in the vitamin C group was 24.9 hours in the trial by Colby et al. However, Colby reported in Table 1 and the text that the SD for the duration of ICU stay was 249.9 hours in their vitamin C group, i.e. 10 times greater than Hu claimed. Such a large error leads to a substantial error in the pooled estimate of effect, but also exaggerates the heterogeneity between the included trials.
Comment [59a] on the Hu (2017) meta-analysis was published 4 years before Dresen’s (2023) paper and was available at PubMed.
... description of history is misleading. Fruit was reported to be beneficial for scurvy two centuries before Lind [2a-2d], so the idea that there was a dietary cause of scurvy was not Lind’s...
 The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36156315>.
 Dresen E, Lee ZY, Hill A, Notz Q, Patel JJ, Stoppe C.
 History of scurvy and use of vitamin C in critical illness: A narrative review. Nutr Clin Pract. 2023
86. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Bias against vitamin C in mainstream medicine: Examples from trials of vitamin C for infections.** Life (Basel). 2022 Jan 3;12(1):62.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35054455>
<https://doi.org/10.3390/life12010062>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8779885>
*The rejection of the demonstrated benefits of vitamin C is largely explained by **three papers published in 1975**—two published in JAMA [see #5, #15, #19] and one in the American Journal of Medicine [see #4 and #17]—all of which have been standard citations in textbooks of medicine and nutrition and in nutritional recommendations. Two of the papers were authored by **Thomas Chalmers**, an influential expert in clinical trials, and the third was authored by **Paul Meier**, a famous medical statistician.*
85. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Assessment of vitamin C effects on pneumonia and COVID-19 using Mendelian randomization: Analysis may be misleading.** Eur J Clin Nutr. 2022;76(9):1347–8.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35165428>
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41430-022-01091-9>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8853427>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358597251>
Hui et al. used single nucleotide polymorphisms that were associated with plasma vitamin C level... However, the cited study states “the variance of plasma vitamin C explained by the 11 lead SNPs was 1.87% on average”. Explaining such a small proportion of the variance is not a valid measure of the possible effects of vitamin C... statistically the analysis by Hui et al. corresponds to the comparison of two population groups of equal size with vitamin C levels of 47.3 vs. 52.7 μM. This is not clinically meaningful when an examination of vitamin C and pneumonia should ideally compare plasma levels between 10–20 μM and 60–100 μM.
 The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34462559>
 Hui LL, Nelson EAS, Lin SL, Zhao JV. The role of vitamin C in pneumonia and COVID-19 infection in adults with European ancestry: a Mendelian randomisation study. Eur J Clin Nutr. 2022

84. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Vitamin C and the risk of atrial fibrillation: Mendelian randomization study may be misleading.** Clin Nutr. 2022;41(6):1446-7.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35545486>
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnu.2022.04.029>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/569672>
 The same problem as in #85.
 The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34537655>
 Chen L, Sun X, Wang Z, Lu Y, Chen M, He Y, Xu H, Zheng L. The impact of plasma vitamin C levels on the risk of cardiovascular diseases and Alzheimer's disease: A Mendelian randomization study. Clin Nutr. 2021 Oct;40(10):5327-5334.
83. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Vitamin C and the risk of cardiovascular diseases: Mendelian randomization study may be misleading.** Eur J Prev Cardiol. 2022;29(9):e291-e292.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35512139>
<https://doi.org/10.1093/eurjpc/zwac067>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/569671>
 The same problem as in #85.
 The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34057996>
 Yuan S, Zheng JS, Mason AM, Burgess S, Larsson SC. Genetically predicted circulating vitamin C in relation to cardiovascular disease. Eur J Prev Cardiol. 2022
82. Hemilä H. **Mendelian randomization study on vitamin C and COVID-19 may be misleading.** PubPeer 2022 June.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20304595>
<https://pubpeer.com/publications/18167AFD057F5E8FA1585C78448D9D#1>
 The same problem as in #85.
 The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35355592>
 Chen S, Zheng C, Chen T, Huang D, Pan Y, Chen S. Relationship Between Plasma Vitamin C and COVID-19 Susceptibility and Severity: A Two-Sample Mendelian Randomization Study. Front Med (Lausanne). 2022 Mar 9;9:844228.
81. Hemilä H. **Mendelian randomization study on vitamin C and the risk of ischemic stroke may be misleading.** PubPeer 2022 June.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20308343>
<https://pubpeer.com/publications/0762DDACF4B99E46B0E6748B998149#1>
 The same problem as in #85.
 The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34796734>
 Martens LG, Luo J, Willems van Dijk K, Jukema JW, Noordam R, van Heemst D. Diet-Derived Antioxidants Do Not Decrease Risk of Ischemic Stroke: A Mendelian Randomization Study in 1 Million People. J Am Heart Assoc. 2021 Dec 7;10(23):e022567.
80. Hemilä H. **Mendelian randomization study on vitamin C and type 2 diabetes may be misleading.** PubPeer 2022 March.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20305117>
<https://pubpeer.com/publications/9E4511840A69941BC6F991118129A5#1>
 The same problem as in #85.
 The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33203707>

Zheng JS, Luan J, Sofianopoulou E, Imamura F, Stewart ID, Day FR, Pietzner M, Wheeler E, et al. Plasma Vitamin C and Type 2 Diabetes: Genome-Wide Association Study and Mendelian Randomization Analysis in European Populations. *Diabetes Care*. 2021 Jan;44(1):98-106.

79. Hemilä H. **Statistical problems in the vitamin C trial with PCI patients by Shafaei-Bajestani et al. (2019)**. PubPeer 2022 February.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19893586>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/1B59AD863839D55215841C1124C2D3#1>

For example:

... Given the errors in the P-values described above, and because the data required for an appropriate analysis are not presented, the statistical significance of the differences in the troponin and CKMB levels between the trial arms cannot be considered to have been established...

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31367642>

Shafaei-Bajestani N, Talasaz AH, Salarifar M, Pourhosseini H, Sadri F, Jalali A. Potential role of vitamin C intracoronary administration in preventing cardiac injury after primary percutaneous coronary intervention in patients with ST-elevation myocardial infarction. *J Res Pharm Pract*. 2019

78. Hemilä H. **Statistical problems in the vitamin C trial with CABG patients by Moludi et al. (2020)**. PubPeer 2022 February.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19894057>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/2E9E504061A7DC2AF6B2692D8632F1#1>

For example:

... In Figure 1, Moludi et al. reported the number of participants for the intervention group as follows: “Allocated to intervention (N=54)” “Lost to follow-up (N=8)” “Analyzed (N=54)”.

It is not clear what “lost to follow-up” means in this context, because the number of randomized and analyzed participants is identical. When all included participants are analyzed, this indicates that no-one was lost to follow-up. The same problem is seen for the control group. This issue is not discussed [1]...

Several parts of the Moludi et al. trial report are confusing and cast doubts on the validity of the published results.

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://doi.org/10.2174/1573401315666190712213051>

<https://www.benthamdirect.com/content/journals/cnf/10.2174/1573401315666190712213051>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343103879>

Jalal Moludi, Mohammad Alizadeh, Godarz Chehri, Hamed Jafari-Vayghyan, Elaheh Foroumandi, Vahid Maleki, Behzad Ebrahimi, Anita Sadeghpour, Azin Alizadehasl and Ali S. Tabaei.

The effect of vitamin C supplementation on cardiac enzymes after coronary artery bypass graft. *Current Nutrition & Food Science* 2020;16(5):833-838.

77. Hemilä H. **Gültekin (2021) paper has a substantial number of identical data with the 20-year earlier Demirag (2001) paper**. PubPeer 2022 February.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19790680>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/8150B66EC0289FA4BF7C9ADB1C48A9#1>

For example:

All six SD values for the LDH published in Gültekin’s Table 3 are identical with 4-digit accuracy to the six SD values reported 20 years earlier in Demirag’s Table 2. Only the order of the SD values for the three groups has been changed...

It does not seem plausible that such a large number of identical findings in two vitamin C papers is explained by chance.

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://doi.org/10.38053/acmj.982137>

<https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/acmj/article/982137>

Yıldırım Gültekin, Abdulkadir Güzel, Atalay Karakaya, Yavuz Beşoğul. Combined effects of the implementation of magnesium and ascorbic acid on myocardial ischemia-reperfusion in open heart surgery. *Anatolian Current Medical Journal* 2021;3(4):319-326.

76. Hemilä H. **Statistical problems in the vitamin C and common cold trial with South Korean army recruits**. *BMJ Mil Health Rapid Response* 2022 March.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19789918>

<https://militaryhealth.bmj.com/content/168/2/117.responses>

For example:

Figure 1 shows that 49 participants were excluded because they “stopped intake of vitamin C”, and 84 participants were excluded because they “stopped intake of placebo”. The CONSORT recommendation for ITT analysis states... “participants who ... did not take all the intended treatment ... exclusion of any participants for such reasons is incompatible with intention-to-treat analysis”.

Altman et al. pointed out that “The odds ratio should not be interpreted as an approximate relative risk [RR] unless the events are rare in both groups (say, less than 20-30%)”. The common cold is not rare. Over 50% of the participants in the Kim et al. trial had the common cold during the trial period which greatly exceeds the 20-30% limit.

... the marginally significant P-value calculated for the over-adjusted statistical model in Table 2 (P = 0.0419) is statistically much less sound than the non-significant P-value calculated in Table 1 (P = 0.059).

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32139409>

Kim TK, Lim HR, Byun JS. Vitamin C supplementation reduces the odds of developing a common cold in Republic of Korea Army recruits: randomised controlled trial. *BMJ Mil Health*. 2022

75. Hemilä H. **Misleading arguments about blinding in vitamin C and zinc lozenge trials by Webster et al. (2021)**. *PubPeer* 2022 March.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20307852>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/FD0F1DC6A711ADF015418581E83038#1>

Webster et al. strongly encourage the assessment of whether blinding had been successful in controlled trials. As an example of cautionary examples on the issue, they refer to trials on vitamin C and zinc lozenges for common cold treatment [1].

*Webster writes: “Aside from the importance of blinding itself, the importance of measuring and reporting blinding success is apparent in various trials. For example, **Karlowksi, et al** [2] compared vitamin C with placebo for treating the common cold...”*

*However, 25 years ago in the same journal I showed that **the Karlowksi trial was analyzed erroneously** [3,4]. Without any explanations, nearly half of the common cold episodes (105 of 249) were excluded from the subgroup analysis that was done by answers to guessing treatment at the end of the trial...*

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33662512>

Webster RK, Bishop F, Collins GS, Evers AWM, Hoffmann T, Knottnerus JA, Lamb SE, Macdonald H, Madigan C, Napadow V, Price A, Rees JL, Howick J.

Measuring the success of blinding in placebo-controlled trials: Should we be so quick to dismiss it? *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2021 Jul;135:176-181.

74. **Retracted. Extra dose of vitamin C based on a daily supplementation shortens the common cold: A meta-analysis of 9 randomized controlled trials.**

Biomed Res Int. 2023;2023:9848057.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37078007>

<https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/9848057>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10110384>

This **retraction** was caused by #73.

... retracted... due to a fundamental error identified in the calculations underlying the conclusions, as raised by readers of the article, Dr. Colby Vorland and Dr. Andrew Brown of the Indiana University School of Public Health-Bloomington, and **Dr. Harri Hemilä** of the University of Helsinki, summarized on PubPeer: <https://pubpeer.com/publications/077EAB95E9141BE6A455C30F0A688E>.

73. Hemilä H. **Shortcomings in the vitamin C and common cold meta-analysis by Ran (2018).**

PubPeer 2021 March.

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/077EAB95E9141BE6A455C30F0A688E#1>

This critique led to the retraction in #74.

For example:

Ran et al. write in the Results section (3.1) that they included 9 trial reports "... after removing duplicates". However, the Lewis (1975) and the Karlowski (1975) reports are about one single trial... Ran et al. write in the Results section (3.3) that "All the studies were 100% completed". This is not the case...

The title states "9 randomized controlled trials". However, Table 2 shows that "random sequence generation" was "unclear" in 4 out of the 8 trials shown in that table. It is not clear why those 4 trials were included if the authors were not convinced that they were randomized...

Another significant statistical problem in the Ran et al. meta-analysis was that participants in the placebo group were double counted...

In conclusion, there are several issues that challenge the validity of the meta-analysis by Ran et al. (2018).

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30069463>

Ran L, Zhao W, Wang J, Wang H, Zhao Y, Tseng Y, Bu H. Extra dose of vitamin C based on a daily supplementation shortens the common cold: A meta-analysis of 9 randomized controlled trials.

Biomed Res Int. 2018

72. Hemilä H. **Flaws in the vitamin C and common cold meta-analysis by Ran et al. (2020).**

PubPeer 2021 February.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20159301>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/A8A31D990B9983EED502D199D2F4F5#1>

See also #73 and #74.

There are numerous problems in the meta-analysis by Ran et al.

The authors write in the inclusion criteria (2.2) that they included trials with "vitamin C as a therapeutic technique with antiviral therapies". However, there is no description of what Ran et al. mean by "antiviral therapies". There are no known antivirals for the common cold.

Transparency is a fundamental principle in science. Ran et al. pool 10 Chinese trials, but it is not possible to check the methods of any of those 10 trials (references 21 to 30). A Google search does not identify any of them...

Reference 22 is puzzling: H. Gao and M. H. Wang, "The analysis of the clinical efficacy of inhalation of vitamin C injection in the treatment of pediatric upper respiratory tract infection," World Latest Medicine Information, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 192, 2014." What does inhalation of vitamin C injection mean? The text section does not mention that the method of administration of vitamin C was highly unusual in the Gao and Wang trial.

Finally, Ran et al. failed to refer to earlier and more extensive meta-analyses on vitamin C and the

common cold. Even more strange is the failure to refer to their own earlier meta-analysis on vitamin C and the common cold. [see #73, #74]

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33102597>

Ran L, Zhao W, Wang H, Zhao Y, Bu H. Vitamin C as a supplementary therapy in relieving symptoms of the common cold: A meta-analysis of 10 randomized controlled trials. Biomed Res Int. 2020

71. Hemilä H, Carr A, Chalker E. **Vitamin C may increase the recovery rate of outpatient cases of SARS-CoV-2 infection by 70%: Reanalysis of the COVID A to Z randomized clinical trial.**

Front Immunol. 2021;12:674681.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34040614>

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2021.674681>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8141621>

For example:

... time to a 50% reduction in symptom duration was 1.2 days shorter in the vitamin C arm than the usual care arm. Given that the observed vitamin C effect was 20% greater than the expected effect (1.2 vs. 1.0),

it is illogical to have stopped the trial early because of “futility”. The authors do not explain this paradox: on the one hand, they considered that a 1.0-day reduction in symptom duration is a clinically important difference, yet on the other hand, the observed 1.2-day reduction was futile and justified early termination. ...

This direct comparison of vitamin C and usual care arms was not published by Thomas et al. Had the authors used appropriate statistical methods, they would have found a statistically significant difference...

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33576820>

Thomas S, Patel D, Bittel B, Wolski K, Wang Q, Kumar A, Il'Giovine ZJ, Mehra R, McWilliams C, Nissen SE, Desai MY. Effect of High-Dose Zinc and Ascorbic Acid Supplementation vs Usual Care on Symptom Length and Reduction Among Ambulatory Patients With SARS-CoV-2 Infection: The COVID A to Z Randomized Clinical Trial. JAMA Netw Open. 2021 Feb 1;4(2):e210369.

70. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Vitamin C and zinc lozenges for COVID-19?** J Am Pharm Assoc. 2021;61(5):e39.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34120854>

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.japh.2021.05.018>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8163692>

We share Marwitz’ concerns regarding widespread misinformation about coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) treatments. However, we do not agree with the statement that “Past examples of vitamin C and zinc, marketed for common cold symptoms, make extensive claims about treating and curing common colds, but the data do not fully support safety and efficacy of these agents”

... regular vitamin C supplementation of at least 0.2 g/d shortened the duration of viral respiratory tract infections in adults by 7.7% (P < 0.001) and in children by 14.2% (P < 0.001). Our review supports the safety and efficacy of vitamin C... the positive findings from randomized trials should not be ignored.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33199166>

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.japh.2020.10.022>

Marwitz KK. The pharmacist’s active role in combating COVID-19 medication misinformation.

J Am Pharm Assoc (2003). 2021

69. Hemilä H. **Flaws in the meta-analysis on mortality in septic patients treated with vitamin C by Scholz et al. (2021).** PubPeer 2021 February.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20307156>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/B48864E0668536925C58F70070746D#1>

There are several methodological shortcomings in the meta-analysis by Scholz et al. [1].

There are two kinds of apples and oranges problem. First, randomized trials and observational studies

are pooled together as if the latter would be as reliable as the former. For firm conclusions, a meta-analysis should be restricted to controlled trials.

Second, the title states “treated with vitamin C”, but the meta-analysis pools studies that investigated vitamin C together with studies that investigated vitamin C combined with hydrocortisone/thiamine. The former studies examine the effects of vitamin C specifically, whereas the latter do not...

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33407793>

Scholz SS, Borgstedt R, Ebeling N, Menzel LC, Jansen G, Rehberg S. Mortality in septic patients treated with vitamin C: a systematic meta-analysis. *Crit Care*. 2021 Jan 6;25(1):17.

68. Hemilä H. **Misleading editorial on the COVID A to Z trial by Michos and Cainzos-Achirica (2021)**. PubPeer 2021 February.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20306924>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/7C275B4F3B2A74D33320D4D9C37AA3#1>

Michos and Cainzos-Achirica write [1] in their editorial about the COVID A to Z trial [2] that “the evidence supporting supplements as a treatment for viral infections is rather limited” [3]. However, reference 3 is a superficial discussion of numerous supplements so that the text on vitamin C is just 135 words long. Michos and Cainzos-Achirica ignore the Cochrane review on vitamin C and the common cold which is 104 pages long [4], and thereby much more relevant source for information on vitamin C and respiratory virus infections.

The Cochrane review reported that 31 comparisons examined the effect of regular vitamin C on 9745 episodes of common cold duration. In adults the duration of colds was reduced by 7.7% (95% CI 3.7% to 11.8%, $P = 0.00018$) and in children by 14.2% (95% CI 7.3% to 21.1%, $P = 0.000053$)”...

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33576814>

Michos ED, Cainzos-Achirica M. Supplements for the Treatment of Mild COVID-19-Challenging Health Beliefs With Science From A to Z. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2021 Feb 1;4(2):e210431.

67. Hemilä H. **Vitamin C is not a placebo equivalent**. PubPeer 2021 March.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20303873>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/0100A772EC303AC9B0F62FDA030E32#1>

In their RCT to test hydroxychloroquine as postexposure prophylaxis to prevent SARS-CoV-2, Barnabas et al. used vitamin C as a placebo [1]: “Households were randomly assigned in a 1:1 ratio to receive either hydroxychloroquine (400 mg/d orally for 3 days, then 200 mg/d orally for an additional 11 days) or **ascorbic acid** (500 mg/d orally for 3 days, then 250 mg/d orally for 11 days) **as a placebo equivalent**.” [bold added]

Vitamin C is not a physiologically inactive substance...

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33284679>

Barnabas RV, Brown ER, Bershteyn A, Stankiewicz Karita HC, Johnston C, Thorpe LE, et al. Hydroxychloroquine as Postexposure Prophylaxis to Prevent Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 Infection: A Randomized Trial. *Ann Intern Med*. 2021 Mar;174(3):344-352.

66. Hemilä H, Carr A. **Comment on “Therapeutic target and molecular mechanism of vitamin C-treated pneumonia: a systematic study of network pharmacology” by R. Li, C. Guo, Y. Li, X. Liang, L. Yang and W. Huang, Food Funct., 2020, 11, 4765.**

Food Funct. 2021;12(3):1371-2.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33449981>

<https://doi.org/10.1039/d0fo02189j>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348531846>

Li et al. ignored studies that found no association between vitamin C intake and the risk of pneumonia...

Li et al. found just 161 VC-treated targets. However, it has been estimated that vitamin C may affect epigenetic regulation of over a thousand different genes in various cell types... Thus, there seem to be

many more genes that may be influenced by vitamin C than those analyzed.

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32420559>

Li R, Guo C, Li Y, Liang X, Yang L, Huang W. Therapeutic target and molecular mechanism of vitamin C-treated pneumonia: a systematic study of network pharmacology. *Food Funct.* 2020

65. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Commentary: Vitamin C supplementation for prevention and treatment of pneumonia.** *Front Med.* 2021;7:595988.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33553198>

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2020.595988>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7854566>

This comment described errors in a **the Cochrane review (2020)** on vitamin C and pneumonia.

For example:

In the section “Criteria for considering studies for this review,” Padhani writes “Types of studies: We included randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and quasi-RCTs.” However, there is no indication that two of the included trials were RCTs or quasi-RCTs...

Padhani further writes “Types of participants: We included studies involving: 1. healthy adults and children receiving vitamin C supplementation for the prevention of pneumonia.” However, Coulehan and Bancalari et al. studied vitamin C for the common cold and neither mentioned pneumonia even as a secondary outcome. Furthermore, Padhani extracted the results of both trials incorrectly...

Padhani did not include a comprehensive discussion of the previous research on vitamin C and pneumonia, and evidence for the safety of vitamin C.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32337708>

Padhani ZA, Moazzam Z, Ashraf A, Bilal H, Salam RA, Das JK, Bhutta ZA. Vitamin C supplementation for prevention and treatment of pneumonia. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2020

64. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Commentary: The long history of vitamin C: From prevention of the common cold to potential aid in the treatment of COVID-19.** *Front Immunol.* 2021;12:659001.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33868305>

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2021.659001>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8047412>

We consider that some of the authors’ statements are inaccurate and here we describe the issues on which we disagree...

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33193359>

Cerullo G, Negro M, Parimbelli M, Pecoraro M, Perna S, Liguori G, Rondanelli M, Cena H, D’Antona G. The Long History of Vitamin C: From Prevention of the Common Cold to Potential Aid in the Treatment of COVID-19. *Front Immunol.* 2020 Oct 28;11:574029.

63. Hemilä H. **Flaws in the inclusion of trials and in referring to earlier meta-analyses.**

PubPeer 2021 January.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20159881>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/3C3BC7155720D6313E0A0EB6091A7B#1>

For example:

Khan et al state in their title “Vitamin C for cardiac protection...” and in their abstract “We address whether intravenous infusion of vitamin C (VC) prior to PCI provides a benefit for cardioprotection”. However, their Table 1 reveals that 4 out of 8 included trials were not “vitamin C” trials...

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32718091>

Khan SA, ET AL. Vitamin C for cardiac protection during percutaneous coronary intervention: A systematic review of randomized controlled trials. *Nutrients.* 2020

62. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Reanalysis of the effect of vitamin C on mortality in the CITRIS-ALI trial: Important findings dismissed in the trial report.** Front Med. 2020;7:590853.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33117837>

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2020.590853>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7575729>

For example:

The trial report states that, “The Kaplan-Meier survival curves for the 2 groups were significantly different by the Wilcoxon test ($\chi^2[1df] = 6.5; P = 0.01$)”. However, this finding was not mentioned in the abstract and it was downplayed in the discussion section...

Fowler et al. calculated $P = 0.01$ for the difference between the survival curves for the vitamin C and placebo groups. However, as shown above, the evidence for vitamin C is much stronger if the analysis is restricted to the four days during which vitamin C was administered, or if two distinct periods for the effect of vitamin C are accounted for.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31573637>

Fowler AA 3rd, Truitt JD, Hite RD, Morris PE, DeWilde C, Priddy A, Fisher B, Thacker LR 2nd, Natarajan R, Brophy DF, Sculthorpe R, Nanchal R, Syed A, Sturgill J, Martin GS, Sevransky J, et al. Effect of Vitamin C Infusion on Organ Failure and Biomarkers of Inflammation and Vascular Injury in Patients With Sepsis and Severe Acute Respiratory Failure: The CITRIS-ALI Randomized Clinical Trial. JAMA. 2019 Oct 1;322(13):1261-1270.

61. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Vitamin C for cardiac surgery patients: Several errors in a published meta-analysis. Comment on “Effects of vitamin C on organ function in cardiac surgery patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis. Nutrients 2019, 11, 2103”.**

Nutrients. 2020;12(2):586.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32102297>

<https://doi.org/10.3390/nu12020586>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7071442>

See the separate supplement which shows the errors in detail:

<https://zenodo.org/records/19733780>

<https://www.mdpi.com/2072-6643/12/2/586/s1>

For example:

The abstract states that “vitamin C significantly decreased ... ventilation time ($p < 0.00001$)”...

This particularly small p-value from Figure 6 is associated with the test of heterogeneity,

not with the test of overall effect ($p = 0.02, Z = 2.27$). In the abstract, this same error occurs for

ICU length of stay and hospital length of stay in that the reported p-values are from the heterogeneity tests,

not from the tests of overall effect. Furthermore, Hill states in Figure 6 that the ventilation time in

the Safaei trial was 15.1 h with 1.0 h standard deviation (SD) in the vitamin C group and 22.9 h (SD 3.8 h)

in the control group. These dispersion estimates were published by Safaei, however, as standard errors (SE) and not SDs.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31487905>

Hill A, Clasen KC, Wendt S, Majoros ÁG, Stoppe C, Adhikari NKJ, Heyland DK, Benstoem C.

Effects of vitamin C on organ function in cardiac surgery patients:

A systematic review and meta-analysis. Nutrients. 2019

Instead of retracting the severely erroneous paper, the editor and authors decided to publish a correction. However, the original PubMed abstract with its errors remains, stating that:

“Vitamin C significantly decreased the incidence of atrial fibrillation ($p = 0.008$),

ventilation time ($p < 0.00001$), ICU length-of-stay ($p = 0.004$), and hospital length-of-stay ($p < 0.0001$).”

That is still false as documented in the above cited critique, compare with p.2 in:

<https://zenodo.org/records/19733780>
<https://www.mdpi.com/2072-6643/12/2/586/s1>

60. Hemilä H. **Misleading editorial on vitamin C in JAMA by Kalil (2020)**. PubPeer 2020 October.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20306020>
<https://pubpeer.com/publications/07DCB1F79D50182367BF913CC69004#1>

For example,

In the editorial on vitamin C in JAMA [1], Kalil writes: “The reported mortality rates were in favor of vitamin C in the other 2 trials [2,3], although in one of those trials [2], the sample size was small (28 patients).” This misleads readers. Logically, a small sample size cannot explain a statistically significant benefit ($P = 0.01$; based on 2/14 vs. 9/14) reported by Zabet [2]. A small sample size can cause a false negative result because of the low statistical power. However, the risk of a false positive finding is not increased when the sample size gets smaller...

Furthermore, two of Kalil’s “vitamin C” studies were not studies about vitamin C...

Finally, the statement by Kalil that “6 [RCTs](including a total of 633 patients)” is false. The actual number of participants in the 6 trials was just 448...

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31950983>

Kalil AC. Lack of Benefit of High-Dose Vitamin C, Thiamine, and Hydrocortisone Combination for Patients With Sepsis. *JAMA*. 2020 Feb 4;323(5):419-420.

59. Hemilä H. **Cochrane has not consistently followed the COPE guidelines**

Eur J Clin Invest. 2020;50(4):e13216.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32077498>

<https://doi.org/10.1111/eci.13216>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/326823>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339396315>

This letter described concerns regarding inappropriate publication practices related to the Cochrane review on vitamin C and asthma.

See also #30, #39, #40.

*In 2009, I found that there were a number of errors in the **Cochrane** review “vitamin C supplementation for asthma”. For example, there were errors in the data extraction; one trial had 20 participants, but only 11 participants were included in the analysis. There were errors in calculations and the unpaired t-test was used when the paired test should have been used. I wrote a feedback which was published in the 2010 version of the review.*

*The managing editor, Emma Welsh, wrote a response in 2012. Simultaneously, **the three Analysis figures, which had been the focus of my critique, were removed. In their absence, however, my feedback though originally valid became irrelevant. Furthermore, the remaining figures were renumbered so that the figure numbers in my feedback indicated real but subsequently changed figures, therefore readers would be completely confused...***

*Analysis figures are the scientific core of Cochrane reviews and their removal after publication seemed inappropriate. **When I found the figure removal, I contacted Cochrane.** As a solution to the problem, the editor-in-chief, David Tovey, proposed that: “I would like to propose that we add a link to the publisher’s note that links people to the version on your website, if, as I expect, I cannot insert a version of the review into the system” (email Tovey 10 June 2016 to Hemilä).*

I responded by email to the effect that to add such a link to the publishers note to my website was inconsistent with COPE² objectives regarding the integrity of the academic record. One issue being that

- 2 COPE. Committee on Publication Ethics.

<https://publicationethics.org>

“The Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (CDSR) is a member of the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE) and follows COPE Core Practices. Cochrane editorial staff, authors, and peer reviewers are expected to understand and follow best practice in publication ethics.”

<https://www.cochranelibrary.com/cdsr/editorial-policies> 2026-5-23

having a link to my website would not be sufficient to guarantee a permanent record as websites of and maintained by individuals are not permanent in the long-run. Furthermore, I saw it as the responsibility of the publisher, not the contributors, to maintain such academic records. (email Hemilä 15 June 2016 to Tovey).

Thereafter, David Tovey proposed that the original publication might be available by email from the Cochrane editors upon request: “we could revise the withdrawn statement as follows: ... Revised statement: ... it is not possible to access the original 2010 version in the review’s history in the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews. Readers should contact the Cochrane Editorial Unit (ceu@cochrane.org) to request a copy of the original version of the review, without the Editors’ changes” (email Tovey 11 March 2017 to Hemilä).

I replied to the above proposal to the effect that to do so was impracticable because a) it put the onus on the reader to write a request to the editors for a copy, b) such a document cannot be used as a reference in future publications, and c) the file itself could be easily lost, especially when future editors take office. Thus, in my opinion, the integrity of the academic record was still compromised (email Hemilä 14 March 2017 to Tovey).

That correspondence took a year and made no further progress, so I contacted COPE. I stated that the removal of the three figures seemed inconsistent with the guidelines to secure the integrity of academic record even in the case of flawed publications. **COPE stated that the original version needs to be made available** and a version with all the original figures was made public in 2018.

Because of the above actions, one single PubMed record (#19160185)³ links to two different versions of the same Cochrane review. The **PubMedCentral (2009)⁴** version includes all the original figures, but not my feedback. **The Cochrane Library (2012)⁵** version includes my feedback, but does not include the three analysis figures to which my feedback focuses. Finally, **a third version (2010)⁶** has both the original figures and my feedback, and is available at the University of Helsinki Digital Archive.

This letter was prompted by the deletion of the original version of the review on vitamin C and asthma, and by the failure to follow appropriate procedures to make the original version available. The removal of three figures, together with the renumbering of the remaining figures by the Cochrane editors, created the misleading impression that Hemilä’s comments were illogical.

See #30 and #39 for the flaws in the Cochrane review on vitamin C and asthma.

The editor-in-chief, David Tovey, did not respond to the above criticism.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19160185>

Kaur B, Rowe BH, Arnold E. Vitamin C supplementation for asthma. Cochrane Database Syst Rev. 2009.

The DOI and PMC links of the PubMed record lead to the different versions of the reviews, see above, with a third version of the “same” report in the University of Helsinki Open Repository.

58. Hemilä H, Friedrich JO. **Many continuous variables should be analyzed using the relative scale: A case study of β_2 -agonists for preventing exercise-induced bronchoconstriction.**

Syst Rev. 2019;8(1):282.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31744533>

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-019-1183-5>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6865024>

... one of the **Cochrane reviews** [53] estimated the effect of vitamin C on EIB on the absolute scale and described the effect of vitamin C five minutes after exercise in the Schachter (1982) trial as follows:

“No significant difference between vitamin C and placebo: Vitamin C mean: -0.24 (SE ± 0.06) L/s, Placebo mean: -0.44 (SE ± 0.14) L/s, $t = 2.13$ ($P = 0.057$)”: Table 2. However, the slope of a linear

3 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19160185> Vitamin C supplementation for asthma (2009) by Balvinder Kaur et al.

4 <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6176494> with all the original figures, no feedback by Hemilä.

5 <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd000993.pub3> with 3 figs deleted, renumbering the remaining, and the feedback.

6 <https://hdl.handle.net/10138/296440> with all the original figures and the feedback by Hemilä.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20373688> with all the original figures and the feedback by Hemilä.

regression analysis of the Schachter study [54], which had reported the IPD, indicated that vitamin C's relative decrease in FEV₁ decline was highly significant: 55% (95% CI: 32 to 78%; P = 0.0003). This difference in P-values also illustrates that the calculation of the absolute effect, which is the custom in the **Cochrane reviews**, can lead to false negative conclusions.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24154977>

Milan SJ, Hart A, Wilkinson M. Vitamin C for asthma and exercise-induced bronchoconstriction. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2013

57. Hemilä H. **Statistical problems in a meta-analysis on vitamin C and critically ill patients by Putzu (2019)**. PubPeer 2019 July.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19856112>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/31E6DF677EC5A16CFBD1908ADACD15#1>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/31E6DF677EC5A16CFBD1908ADACD15#3>

For example,

The title of a recent review in Critical Care Medicine by Putzu et al. indicated that their focus was the specific effect of vitamin C for critically ill patients. The abstract describes that they “included randomized controlled trials on the use of vitamin C (any regimen) in adult critically ill patients versus placebo or no therapy”, though the reader does not know what the “any regimen” means in the context. However, Table 1 of the review shows that only five of the 16 included ICU trials were vitamin C trials. Eleven of the included ICU trials administered vitamin C together with vitamins A, B, or E, or with selenium, zinc, etc. Thus, those 11 trials do not test the specific effect of vitamin C on ICU patients. The other substances can have negative or positive effects of their own, biasing the analysis of vitamin C effects. In the field of meta-analysis, combining results of trials which are too different, is referred to as the apples and oranges problem.

Putzu et al. also included some trials twice. In subgroup analysis 2.1.2 of eFigure 8, Putzu includes both the Sadeghpour and the Moludi trials.

In subgroup analysis 2.4.2 of eFigure 9, Putzu includes both the Alshafey and the Retz trials... Evidently, a single trial is also included twice in this case.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30839358>

Putzu A, Daems AM, Lopez-Delgado JC, Giordano VF, Landoni G. The effect of vitamin C on clinical outcome in critically ill patients: A systematic review with meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Crit Care Med*. 2019

56. Hemilä H. **Misleading meta-analysis on vitamin C and critically ill patients by Langlois (2019)**. PubPeer 2019 April.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19855542>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/D661E94CBDF6C6A9C04B8ACCD32DFC#1>

For example,

The title of a recent review in JPEN by Langlois et al. indicated that their focus was the specific effect of vitamin C for critically ill patients. Furthermore, the abstract describes that they searched “for RCTs comparing vitamin C, by enteral or parenteral routes, with placebo or none, in intensive care unit (ICU) patients.” However, Table 1 of the review shows that only two of the included 11 trials were vitamin C trials. Nine of the included trials administered vitamin C with vitamins A, B, or E, or with selenium, zinc, etc. Thus, those nine trials do not test the specific effect of vitamin C. The other substances can have negative or positive effects of their own, biasing the analysis of vitamin C effects.

Langlois et al. wrote that the length of ICU stay “was reported by 8 of the 11 RCTs, but only 5 trials reported data as mean and SD, allowing statistical aggregation”. Only one of the five trials included in that analysis tested vitamin C alone. Thus, the four other trials tested vitamin C together with other substances.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30452091>

Langlois PL, Manzanares W, Adhikari NKJ, Lamontagne F, Stoppe C, Hill A, Heyland DK. Vitamin C Administration to the Critically Ill: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. JPEN J Parenter Enteral Nutr. 2019

55. Hemilä H. **Random-effects assumption in meta-analyses.** JAMA. 2019;322(1):81.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31265091>

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2019.5439>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/312604>

One meta-analysis on vitamin C and postoperative atrial fibrillation used the random-effects meta-analysis approach to describe data from 13 trials and calculated that vitamin C was associated with a decreased occurrence of postoperative atrial fibrillation with a relative risk (RR) of 0.68 (95% CI, 0.54-0.87). However, heterogeneity was significant with an I^2 of 59% ($P = .003$).⁷ Although the confidence interval indicates that vitamin C was associated with a decreased risk, at least in some hospital contexts, it is not evident which patients should take vitamin C or which patient groups should be investigated in further trials.

Another meta-analysis used the subgroup analysis approach and calculated that among 5 trials conducted in the United States, vitamin C did not prevent postoperative atrial fibrillation (RR, 1.04; 95% CI, 0.86-1.27). However, in 9 trials conducted outside the United States in lower-income countries, vitamin C was associated with a decreased incidence of postoperative atrial fibrillation (RR, 0.56; 95% CI, 0.47-0.67).⁸ These subgroup findings indicate that new trials in the United States may be a waste of resources, whereas further research conducted in lower-income countries should be encouraged. Such conclusions cannot, however, be drawn from the single confidence interval from the random-effects meta-analysis.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30566189>

Serghiou S, Goodman SN. Random-effects meta-analysis: Summarizing evidence with caveats. JAMA. 2019

54. Hemilä H. **Misleading review on vitamin C and cardiac patients**

by Hill et al. (2018). PubPeer 2019 May.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19789076>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/DEBED5D9F498A0C940E18841C25C75#1>

For example,

Page 4 of the PDF version of Hill et al. states: “Fowler et al observed ... a reduced 28-day mortality after the application of vitamin C in patients with sepsis and multi-organ-failure.” This is based on Fowler’s Supplementary table 1, where he published that 62.5% of placebo participants died, but only 50.6% of high vitamin C dosage participants died. However, there were just 8 participants in both groups. This means that 5 of 8 participants died in the placebo group, and 4 of 8 participants died in the vitamin C group. This gives $P(2-t) = 1.0$ in the Fisher’s exact test.

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30060468>

Hill A, Wendt S, Benstoem C, Neubauer C, Meybohm P, Langlois P, Adhikari NK, Heyland D, Stoppe C. Vitamin C to improve organ dysfunction in cardiac surgery patients – Review and pragmatic approach. Nutrients. 2018

7 Shi R, Li ZH, Chen D, Wu QC, Zhou XL, Tie HT. Sole and combined vitamin C supplementation can prevent postoperative atrial fibrillation after cardiac surgery: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. Clin Cardiol. 2018

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29603289>

8 Hemilä H, Suonsyrjä T. Vitamin C for preventing atrial fibrillation in high risk patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis. BMC Cardiovasc Disord. 2017

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28143406>

53. Vorilhon P, Arpajou B, Roussel HV, Merlin É, Pereira B, Cabailot A.
Retraction note: Efficacy of vitamin C for the prevention and treatment of upper respiratory tract infection: A meta-analysis in children. Eur J Clin Pharmacol. 2021;77(6):941.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33988724>

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00228-021-03150-9>

This **retraction** was caused by #51 and #52.

After publication, **a reader has identified some mistakes** in the data reported, these include the following:

(i) Inclusion of studies which did not meet strict inclusion criteria: one with pseudo randomization allocation and another one with the intervention group receiving vitamin C and herbal preparation containing Echinacea and propolis which is relatively heavily weighted and has one of the strongest effects in the analysis of primary and secondary outcomes.

(ii) Some data, numbers of upper respiratory tract infection (URTI) episodes and standard-deviations of URTI durations, extracted from studies were erroneous.

(iii) Some statistical approaches performed in our meta-analysis are not appropriate and have not been described accurately. These errors are likely to invalidate the results.

The authors acknowledge and apologize for these involuntary errors. For these reasons, the article has been retracted.

52. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Vitamin C and the common cold in children: Severe flaws in the meta-analyses by Vorilhon (2019).** University of Helsinki Open Repository 2021.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6395731>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/333365>

This critique and #51 led to the retraction in #53.

In 2019, Philippe Vorilhon et al. published a meta-analysis on vitamin C for the prevention and treatment of upper respiratory tract infections in children [1]. In a letter to the editor we pointed out several errors in the meta-analysis [2]. Vorilhon et al. responded to our criticism [3], but we did not feel their responses were satisfactory (section 3 in the Main Document).

Since the publication of Vorilhon's response we delved into Vorilhon's meta-analyses in more detail. Specifics of the data extraction were not clear in Vorilhon's paper [1] and some of the trial data shown in their forest plots are questionable. We therefore reconstructed the tables from Vorilhon's meta-analysis (sections 1 and 2 of the Main Document).

The top section of the Figure below shows the reconstruction of Vorilhon's meta-analysis on common cold duration, and the bottom section shows the meta-analysis of the same trials with the correct data. Several errors in Vorilhon's meta-analysis can be seen when comparing the two sections of the figure.

Firstly, the Cohen (2004) trial [4] is not included in the corrected meta-analysis, since it was not a vitamin C trial [2] (Main Document p 27). Secondly, in the Vorilhon analysis, there were errors in the reported numbers of observations in every trial, compare the upper and lower sections. Thirdly, in the Ritzel (1961) and Miller (1977) trials [5,6], Vorilhon used SD estimates that were inconsistent with the data published in the trial reports (Main Document pp 13,16). In this summary, we briefly describe a few of the major errors (details in the Main Document).

...

The errors described above and in the Main Document are not inconsequential. In the abstract, Vorilhon wrote that "Vitamin C administration was found to decrease the duration of URTI by 1.6 days (standardized mean differences = -0.30 [-0.53; -0.08], $p = 0.009$)" [1]. This is the pooled result shown on the top section of the Figure below. However, correct extraction of data, imputation of SD values consistent with published information, and excluding the Cohen trial that was not a vitamin C trial would lead to a revision of that statement to: "Vitamin C administration was not found to decrease the duration of URTI (standardized mean differences = -0.15 [-0.31; +0.01], $p = 0.072$)." This is the pooled result shown on the bottom section of the Figure below. Thus, correction of all the errors leads to a change from a statistically

highly significant benefit to no significant difference between the treatment groups. This error is present in the abstract [1], and therefore particularly concerning.

Vitamin C may have an impact on the duration and severity of colds in children [9], but because of the severe errors in the meta-analysis, no conclusions can be drawn on this matter from Vorilhon's study [1]. Nevertheless, Vorilhon's paper is not the only one on vitamin C and respiratory infections that has been shown to be flawed. Unfortunately, many other reviews and other texts on vitamin C and respiratory infections have been shown to contain errors [10-22].

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30465062>

Vorilhon P, Arpajou B, Vaillant Roussel H, Merlin É, Pereira B, Cabaillet A. Efficacy of vitamin C for the prevention and treatment of upper respiratory tract infection. A meta-analysis in children. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol.* 2019

51. Hemilä H, Chalker E. **Meta-analysis on vitamin C and the common cold in children may be misleading.** *Eur J Clin Pharmacol.* 2019;75(12):1747-8.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31377890>

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00228-019-02733-x>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/318103>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334946593>

See the supplement separately:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6395644>

https://static-content.springer.com/esm/art%3A10.1007%2Fs00228-019-02733-x/MediaObjects/228_2019_2733_MOESM1_ESM.pdf

This critique and #52 led to the retraction in #53.

Vorilhon et al. reported a meta-analysis in which they examined the effect of vitamin C on common cold in children. Nevertheless, we do not consider that their conclusions are valid. Our main concerns are summarized below. We include further issues and details in a supplementary file...

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30465062>

Vorilhon P, Arpajou B, Vaillant Roussel H, Merlin É, Pereira B, Cabaillet A. Efficacy of vitamin C for the prevention and treatment of upper respiratory tract infection. A meta-analysis in children. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol.* 2019

50. Hemilä H. **Errors in a meta-analysis on vitamin C and post-operative atrial fibrillation.**

Int J Surg. 2019;64:66.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30831247>

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsu.2019.01.025>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/312582>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331467905>

Hu et al. stated in their methods that “studies that met the following criteria were included: randomized controlled trials (RCTs) of adult patients who underwent cardiac surgery; patients randomly assigned to receive vitamin C or placebo ... Any studies of non-randomized designs ... were excluded”. However,

Hu included the study by Carnes et al. although that was not an RCT...

In their Fig. 4, Hu et al. stated that the standard deviation (SD) of the mean duration of ICU stay in the vitamin C group was 24.9 hours in the trial by Colby et al. However, Colby reported in their Table 1 and text that the SD for the duration of ICU stay was 249.9 hours in their vitamin C group, i.e. 10 times greater than Hu claimed...

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27956113>

Hu X, Yuan L, Wang H, Li C, Cai J, Hu Y, Ma C. Efficacy and safety of vitamin C for atrial fibrillation after cardiac surgery: A meta-analysis with trial sequential analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Int J Surg.* 2017

49. Hemilä H. **Biased editorial on vitamin C in JAMA by Brant and Angus (2019).**

PubPeer 2020 October.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20157034>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/6C1E79E2B8EA7E2DEED9B46C2B717C#1>

In their editorial on vitamin C in JAMA, Brant and Angus write: “Although unproven, common folklore holds that orange juice and lemons speed recovery from both influenza and the common cold, apparently due to a boost to the immune system. Linus Pauling, winner of 2 Nobel prizes, claimed a beneficial role for vitamin C across a wide range of diseases...” [1].

This misleads readers. Linus Pauling carried out a meta-analysis – one of the very first in medicine – in which he concluded that vitamin C is beneficial against the common cold [2]. From 4 placebo-controlled trials, Pauling calculated that it was highly unlikely that the benefits reported in the vitamin C groups were explained by chance alone with $P = 0.000022$ [2]. Further controlled trials have corroborated Pauling’s conclusions [3-7].... They also write “Linus Pauling, winner of 2 Nobel prizes, claimed a beneficial role for vitamin C across a wide range of diseases, including terminal cancer (Ref 3)” [1].

This is also misleading. Reference 3 is not a paper on vitamin C and cancer, but Pauling’s paper on vitamin C and evolution [10]. Thereby Brant and Angus make it seem that Pauling did not have any empirical basis for his opinions on vitamin C and cancer. In fact, Pauling published 2 clinical studies on vitamin C and cancer in PNAS [11-13] and a long review on the biological plausibility of vitamin C effect in Cancer Research [14], but these papers were hidden from the readers of the editorial...

Etc.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31573621>

Brant EB, Angus DC. Is High-Dose Vitamin C Beneficial for Patients With Sepsis?

JAMA. 2019 Oct 1;322(13):1257-1258.

48. Hemilä H. **Misleading meta-analysis on vitamin C for sepsis patients by Li (2018).**

PubPeer 2019 September.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20305849>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/2D26F22CEA264D1B84910D89AD26D7#1>

The Li study (1) is a meta-analysis which pooled the findings of a before–after study (2) with the findings of two small RCTs (3,4). This meta-analysis has several shortcomings which diminish the validity of the findings.

Firstly, the inclusion criteria were flawed. Observational studies may be biased due to confounding. Therefore, in evidence-based medicine, researchers almost always consider only randomised controlled trails...

In addition, the statistical analysis in the Li meta-analysis was not optimal. For binary outcomes, Li (1) calculated the pooled odds ratio (OR). However, the OR is appropriate for rare outcomes, but not for common outcomes. For common outcomes, the OR exaggerates the effects and should not be used (5-11).

For continuous outcomes, Li calculated the standardized mean difference (SMD), which uses one standard deviation (SD) as the unit of the scale. However, such a scale is difficult for medical readers to interpret...

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30305111>

Li J. Evidence is stronger than you think: a meta-analysis of vitamin C use in patients with sepsis.

Crit Care. 2018 Oct 11;22(1):258.

47. Hemilä H. **Zinc lozenges and vitamin C for high-performance athletes.**

British J Sport Medicine Rapid Response 2018 May 18.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20305699>

<https://bjsm.bmj.com/content/52/7/439.responses>

... Maughan et al. did not mention at all the effect of vitamin C on exercise-induced bronchoconstriction [EIB]. Three double-blind placebo-controlled cross-over RCTs found that vitamin C decreased exercise-induced FEV₁ decline by 48% (95% CI 33% to 64%) [9,10]. Only some athletes suffer

from EIB, yet for them it may be worthwhile to test on an individual basis whether vitamin C has efficacy.

Maugham et al. further wrote that for vitamin C, “immune measures [are] no different from placebo” [1, Table 4]. This statement is misleading for readers. A search of the PubMed for reviews on vitamin C and immunity identifies dozens of reports. Reviews have shown that there is a large number of studies indicating that vitamin C does have effects on the immune system, three of which I cite here [12-14]. The published effects on the immune system do not indicate whether vitamin C has practical relevance, but it is misleading to claim that the effects of vitamin C on immune measures are no different from placebo [1].

Finally, Maugham et al. wrote that “Cochrane reviews show no benefit of initiating vitamin C supplementation (>200 mg/day) after onset of URS” and they cited refs 100,101 in their review [1, Table 4]. First, Maugham’s reference 101 is not a Cochrane review. Second, absence of evidence is not evidence of absence [15].

In our Cochrane review (ref. 100 in Maugham’s paper), we wrote that from a methodological perspective, therapeutic trials are much more complicated than regular supplementation trials [11]. We gave examples of factors that may influence the efficacy of vitamin C, such as the timing of supplementation initiation, the duration of supplementation, and the dosage. Inappropriate selection of any of these factors might give rise to false negative findings in a therapeutic trial. We should therefore be cautious in the interpretation of the published therapeutic trials. Furthermore, we pointed out that “The larger effect observed using 8 g [of vitamin C] compared with 4 g as a single dose in the Anderson 1974f trial and the dose dependency in the Karlowski 1975a trial suggest that future therapeutic trials with adults should use doses of at least 8 g/day” [11]; see also [16].

It thus misleads readers to claim that our Cochrane review (ref. 100 in Maugham’s paper) “show[s] no benefit of initiating vitamin C supplementation after [the] onset of URS” [1].

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29540367>

Maughan RJ, Burke LM, Dvorak J, Larson-Meyer DE, Peeling P, Phillips SM, Rawson ES, Walsh NP, Garthe I, Geyer H, Meeusen R, van Loon LJC, Shirreffs SM, Spriet LL, Stuart M, Vernec A, Currell K, Ali VM, Budgett RG, Ljungqvist A, Mountjoy M, Pitsiladis YP, Soligard T, Erdener U, Engebretsen L. IOC consensus statement: dietary supplements and the high-performance athlete. Br J Sports Med. 2018 Apr;52(7):439-455.

46. Hemilä H. **Publication bias in meta-analysis of ascorbic acid for postoperative atrial fibrillation.**

Am J Health Syst Pharm. 2017;74(6):372-3.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28274978>

<https://doi.org/10.2146/ajhp160999>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/312602>

... These instances of publication not being sought because of negative results illustrate publication bias. Furthermore, a small trial conducted by Healy et al., whose results appeared in abstract form only, was omitted from Baker and Coleman’s meta-analysis. Baker and Coleman used a statistical test to determine whether there might be publication bias in their meta-analysis and stated that “no significant publication bias was noted (Egger’s $p = 0.13$).” However, such a theoretical calculation does not provide definitive evidence about whether publication bias actually does or does not exist. The omission of the aforementioned unpublished studies illustrates that publication bias did exist in Baker and Coleman’s meta-analysis and flawed their estimate of the effect of ascorbic acid.

Baker and Coleman stated that “only RCTs that compared ascorbic acid with a placebo or other control were included” in their review, but they included the study by Carnes et al. even though it was not an RCT. Strangely enough, Baker and Coleman stated that “one study did not involve random sequence generation” and referred to the study of Carnes et al., yet that study was included in their review. The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27806938>

Baker WL, Coleman CI. Meta-analysis of ascorbic acid for prevention of postoperative atrial fibrillation after cardiac surgery. Am J Health Syst Pharm. 2016

45. Hemilä H. **Erroneous calculation of sample size in a vitamin C and atrial fibrillation trial.** J Cardiol. 2017;69(6):895.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27956046>
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jjcc.2016.10.010>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/299253>
... Furthermore, those authors observed 7 cases of AF among 52 vitamin C patients and 10 cases of AF among 53 control patients. This leads to a risk ratio (RR) 0.713 that corresponds to 29.7% lower incidence of AF in the vitamin C group. This difference is greater than the 20% effect that was the basis for the sample size calculation by the authors, yet the difference was not statistically significant because the number of patients was so small.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26917198>
 Antonic M, Lipovec R, Gregorcic F, Juric P, Kosir G. Perioperative ascorbic acid supplementation does not reduce the incidence of postoperative atrial fibrillation in on-pump coronary artery bypass graft patients. J Cardiol. 2017
44. Hemilä H. **Vitamin C in clinical therapeutics.** Clin Ther. 2017;39(10):2110-2.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28863879>
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinthera.2017.08.005>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228957>
I read with great interest Dr Shader's editorial that discussed vitamin C. I share many of his concerns about methodologic and statistical problems in the vitamin C trials. Nevertheless, some of my conclusions of the field are more positive...
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28420486>
 Shader RI. Vitamins C and D. Clin Ther. 2017
43. Hemilä H. **Thomas Chalmers, vitamin C and the common cold.** J R Soc Med. 2016;109(2):46.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26880652>
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0141076815606279>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC4793763>
 See #4 and #17, and footnote 21.
Kay Dickersin and Frances Chalmers wrote that Thomas Chalmers "contributed substantially to the wave of meta-analyses in medicine which took off during the late 1970s and 1980s". Chalmers' meta-analysis on vitamin C and the common cold was mentioned as an example of the studies that provided statistically more robust estimates of treatment effects, but that is an unfortunate example.
In his 1975 meta-analysis, Thomas Chalmers calculated of seven placebo-controlled trials that common cold episodes were 0.11 ± 0.24 (SE) days shorter for the vitamin C groups than for the placebo groups. I showed in 1995 that in some cases Chalmers presented data that were inconsistent with the original data. Chalmers also made errors in the calculations and ignored the doses, and his selection of trials was inconsistent. I analysed the studies Chalmers had identified for which ≥ 1 g/d of vitamin C had been used and calculated that common cold episodes were 0.93 ± 0.22 (SE) days shorter in the vitamin C groups.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26085561>
 Dickersin K, Chalmers F. Thomas C Chalmers (1917-1995): a pioneer of randomised clinical trials and systematic reviews. J R Soc Med. 2015
42. Hemilä H. **Evidence-based management of EIB with vitamin C.** BMJ Rapid Response 2016 February 29.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20157559>
<https://www.bmj.com/content/352/bmj.h6951/rr>
Smoliga, Weiss and Rundell reviewed exercise-induced bronchoconstriction (EIB) and implied in their title that they covered evidence-based managements of EIB.

EBM requires that the literature searches should be thorough, and RCTs and systematic reviews should be the primary focus of the searches. There are 3 RCTs on vitamin C and EIB and the pooled relative effect estimate indicates a 48% reduction (95% CI 33% to 64%) in the postexercise FEV₁ decline when vitamin C was administered before exercise [1,2]. These findings were not mentioned by Smoliga et al.

A subcommittee of the American Thoracic Society wrote guidelines about EIB and in the guidelines mentioned 2 RCTs about vitamin C [3]. I pointed out that a third RCT had been ignored in the guidelines, and I also pointed out that the statistical analysis of the 2 included RCTs was superficial, eg 95% CIs were not calculated [4]. Rundell was an author of the guidelines [3] and thus knew that there are RCTs on vitamin C and EIB.

Dismissing the evidence about vitamin C for EIB may be explained by the bias in mainstream medicine against treatments that do not need prescriptions [5].

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26762594>

Smoliga JM, Weiss P, Rundell KW. Exercise induced bronchoconstriction in adults: evidence based diagnosis and management. *BMJ*. 2016 Jan 13;352:h6951.

41. Hemilä H. **Zinc lozenges and vitamin C for the common cold are not examples of placebo effect in action.** *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2015;68(12):1524-5.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26071891>

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2015.05.012>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228079>

See #5, #6, #19.

In the introduction to their article on the reporting of blinding in trial publications, Bello et al. write that compromised blinding has raised concerns and, as examples, refer to studies on zinc lozenges and vitamin C for the common cold.

In 1975, Karlowski et al. concluded from their vitamin C and common cold trial that “the effects [of ascorbic acid] demonstrated might be explained equally well by a break in the double blind.” The placebo consisted of lactose, which is easily distinguishable from ascorbic acid by taste. Statisticians and clinical trialists have frequently cited the Karlowski study in textbooks, the CONSORT statement, and other publications as an example of the placebo effect in action. In 1996, however, I showed in this journal that the Karlowski report contained erroneous analysis. For example, 42% of the common cold episodes were missing from the comparison of the “blinded” vs. “unblinded” participants although Karlowski presented those two groups as if they were complementary. Karlowski's placebo effect explanation also contains several other problems. Over two dozen trials with valid placebos, such as citric acid, have clearly shown that the effects of vitamin C on the common cold are not placebo effects. Because the benefits of vitamin C demonstrated in the Karlowski trial are consistent with those observed in other studies, the Karlowski trial should not be claimed as an example of placebo effect in action.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24973822>

Bello S, Moustgaard H, Hróbjartsson A. The risk of unblinding was infrequently and incompletely reported in 300 randomized clinical trial publications. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2014

40. Kaur B, Rowe BH, Stovold E. **WITHDRAWN: Vitamin C supplementation for asthma.** *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2013;2013(10):CD000993.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24155047>

<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd000993.pub4>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6176495>

This **withdrawal** was because of the criticism in #30 and #39.

See also #59 about the Cochrane publication ethics problems, inconsistent with COPE Guidelines.

*A previous version of this review, published on 21 January 2009, received comments from **H. Hemilä** (Department of Public Health, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland) [see #30]. In response to this feedback*

the review was updated and published on 20 June 2012 [PMID: 19160185], as follows: (1) removed three instances of reporting of baseline lung function values; and (2) deleted statistical data from a trial that only reported data on participants who benefited from treatment.

The parts of the review affected by these changes are the section on Effects of interventions, the first paragraph of the Discussion section, and Data and Analyses Table 1: Oral vitamin C vs placebo (single-dose studies).

The uncorrected version of the review (published 21 January 2009) is no longer available in the **Cochrane Database** of Systematic Reviews, but can be accessed via PubMed Central: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6176494>.

This Cochrane review on vitamin C and asthma misled readers for a decade from 2001 to 2013.

See the PubMed records of the Cochrane review on vitamin C and asthma from 2001 to 2013:

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/11687089> 2001

<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD000993>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/1A7012E6FC3DD45579594F967CB38D#1>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15266435> 2004

<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD000993.pub2>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/02056F97D4305CB49D3E8DA85052B1#1>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19160185> 2009

<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD000993.pub3>

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/1A7012E6FC3DD45579594F967CB38D#1>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24155047> 2013 Withdrawal of the Cochrane review

<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD000993.pub4>

39. Hemilä H. **Vitamin C and exercise-induced bronchoconstriction: Further problems in the Cochrane review “vitamin C for asthma” (2012)**. University of Helsinki Open Repository 2013.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6405803>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/40816>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/272094448>

See #30, #59.

This comment was partly the cause for the withdrawal in #40.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19160185>

Kaur B, Rowe BH, Arnold E. Vitamin C supplementation for asthma. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2009. **The DOI and PMC links of the PubMed record lead to two different versions of the “same” review, and a third version of the “same” review is available at the University of Helsinki Open Repository, see the background for these versions in #59.**

38. Hemilä H, Al-Biltagi M, Baset AA. **Retraction: Vitamin C and asthma in children: Modification of the effect by age, exposure to dampness and the severity of asthma**. *Clin Transl Allergy*. 2012;2(1):6.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22423606>

<https://doi.org/10.1186/2045-7022-2-6>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3320558>

After our paper was published, we found out severe problems in the data set. There were 60 children in the study. The ages were by accident duplicated between the upper and lower halves of the database. Thus, the ages for the first 30 children in the data set were identical and in the same order with the ages for the second set of 30 children. Similar duplication was also found for C-ACT and FEV₁ measurements after vitamin C supplementation and for exposure to dampness.

This is **the retracted** paper, retracted because of severe errors in the Egyptian data set:

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22409829>

Hemilä H, Al-Biltagi M, Baset AA. Vitamin C and asthma in children: modification of the effect by age, exposure to dampness and the severity of asthma. Clin Transl Allergy. 2011

The errors in the Egyptian data set also led to the **retraction** of an earlier 2009 paper by the Egyptian authors:

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22970440>

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1651-2227.2012.02723.x>

The following article ... has been retracted by agreement between the authors, the journal Editor-in-Chief, Hugo Lagercrantz, and Blackwell Publishing Ltd. The retraction has been agreed because of unintentional errors in the analysis of the data presented.

The earlier 2009 report by the Egyptian authors:

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19154523>

Biltagi MA, Baset AA, Bassiouny M, Kasrawi MA, Attia M. Omega-3 fatty acids, vitamin C and Zn supplementation in asthmatic children: a randomized self-controlled study. Acta Paediatr. 2009

37. Hemilä H. **The effect of vitamin C on the common cold.** J Pharm Pract. 2011;24(2):241-2.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21712220>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228058>

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0897190010392376>

Since the conclusions of the Cochrane review diverge considerably from the conclusions of Mathes and Bellanger, it is useful to look at the findings of the studies they refer to. Some of the findings are inconsistent with their statements... These 7 controlled trials described above do not support Mathes and Bellanger's statements although the studies are provided as references. Furthermore, Mathes and Bellanger do not describe their rationalization to select the 9 references out of several dozens. In systematic reviews, it is important to describe the selection criteria, in order to prevent bias caused by selecting studies that are consistent with the reviewers' preconceptions. If Mathes and Bellanger were not ready to carry out their own systematic review, they should have taken a look at the Cochrane review which used explicit selection criteria and included all studies fulfilling those criteria...

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21507804>

Mathes A, Bellanger R. Herbs and other dietary supplements: current regulations and recommendations for use to maintain health in the management of the common cold or other related infectious respiratory illnesses. J Pharm Pract. 2010

The authors of the CE article, "Herbs and Other Dietary Supplements: Current Regulations and Recommendations for Use to Maintain Health in the Management of the Common Cold or Other Related Infectious Respiratory Illnesses" have no comments.

36. Hemilä H. **Randomised trials on vitamin C.** Br J Nutr. 2011;105(3):485-7.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20979683>

<https://doi.org/10.1017/s000711451000351x>

Given their title and introduction, one would expect a discussion about randomised controlled trials (RCT) on vitamin C and the common cold. However, this topic is ignored in their review. This is an unfortunate omission because the common cold studies give interesting information on the issues that Lykkesfeldt and Poulsen discuss... Finally, the title of Lykkesfeldt and Poulsen's paper emphasises RCT, whereas a large part of their text discusses cohort studies. Accordingly, the title and text are inconsistent. Dietary factors correlate strongly with each other and with numerous other lifestyle factors. Therefore, the correlations between dietary vitamin C intake and health outcomes can be explained by residual confounders.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20003627>

Lykkesfeldt J, Poulsen HE. Is vitamin C supplementation beneficial? Lessons learned from randomised controlled trials. *Br J Nutr.* 2010

35. Hemilä H. **Vitamin C and the common cold: Early systematic reviews and the justification for new trials.** PLOS Medicine Reader comment on 2010 October 27.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20158813>

<https://journals.plos.org/plosmedicine/article/comment?id=10.1371/annotation/fb95fbc7-ba3a-4a8a-be82-5a722770ecf0>

See also #4, #17, #43.

Vitamin C and the common cold is a particularly important topic in the history of systematic reviews because three of the earliest systematic reviews examined that topic. Nevertheless, Bastian et al.'s brief mention of this issue is misleading...

*In their Box 1, Bastian et al. list **Chalmers' 1975 systematic review** as one of the early systematic reviews, without mentioning that the review was shown to be seriously flawed over a decade ago. At the same time **Bastian et al. ignore Pauling's 1971 systematic reviews although they were methodologically sound and published 3 years before the first systematic review mentioned in Box 1.** Given that the primary purpose of systematic reviews is to minimize the likelihood of being misled by the effects of biases, Bastian et al.'s biased presentation of the early systematic reviews is amazing.*

I dont see much justification for Bastian et al.'s proposal that a new controlled trial should not be carried out unless a systematic review has shown the trial to be necessary. If researchers had been following Bastian et al.'s way of reasoning, no new vitamin C common cold trials would have been carried out after Chalmers' 1975 systematic review was published. Although that review largely quelled interest in vitamin C, it is fortunate that some new trials were still carried out. Our Cochrane review shows that even more new trials are needed. I have read many poor quality systematic reviews and it would be a pity if all of them had such a great influence that the justification for new trials was based on them. Given that Bastian et al. cannot see that the highly influential Chalmers' 1975 systematic review is seriously flawed, how could less experienced researchers evaluate whether some of the recent systematic reviews is reliable or not when they are contemplating the rationale for a new trial..

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20877712>

Bastian H, Glasziou P, Chalmers I. Seventy-five trials and eleven systematic reviews a day: how will we ever keep up? *PLoS Med.* 2010

34. Hemilä H. **Citation bias in the CONSORT 2010 comments on blinding.**

BMJ Rapid Response 2010 May 18.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20308613>

<https://www.bmj.com/rapid-response/2011/11/02/citation-bias-consort-comments-blinding>

In their discussion on the CONSORT guidelines for clinical trial reporting, Moher et al. state that accurate and transparent reporting are important (1). About blinding, they write as follows: "Participants may respond differently if they are aware of their treatment assignment ... These biases have been well documented" (6 citations).

*One of the six cited papers is the trial by **Karlowski et al.** (2) which reported that the benefit of vitamin C against the common cold was explained by the break in the blind. In the abstract: [the vitamin C] "effects demonstrated might be explained equally well by a break in the double blind" (2). The Karlowski trial has frequently been cited by clinical trialists as an example of the importance of blinding, and by specialists in nutrition and infectious diseases as an evidence that vitamin C does not have a real effect on the common cold (3,4) ...*

Over a decade ago, I pointed out the problems of the Karlowski subgroup analysis (4). The principal investigator of the Karlowski trial did not find errors in my reanalysis (6,7). The study cannot be considered as an example of placebo effect in action.

The authors had not responded to the criticism by 2026.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20332511>

Moher D, Hopewell S, Schulz KF, Montori V, Gøtzsche PC, Devereaux PJ, Elbourne D, Egger M, Altman DG. CONSORT 2010 explanation and elaboration: updated guidelines for reporting parallel group randomised trials. *BMJ* 2010;340:c869.

33. Hemilä H. **Vitamin C for the common cold should not be rejected on the basis of old and erroneous articles.** *J Allergy Clin Immunol.* 2009;124(4):859.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19660806>

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaci.2009.06.015>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228310>

Mainardi *et al*¹ reviewed the use and effects of complementary and alternative medicines on respiratory symptoms. They stated that early studies on vitamin C did not demonstrate an effect on the duration or intensity of the common cold, and as a support to this statement, they referred to 2 articles from 1975.^{2,3}

I showed a decade ago that the **Karlowski trial** was erroneously analyzed.^{4,5,6} The authors argued that the results of their placebo-controlled double-blind trial might be explained, paradoxically, by the placebo effect. However, their suggestion was based on a subgroup analysis in which they excluded 42% of recorded common cold episodes without any justification

... for a reader it would have been more useful to refer to an up-to-date review that covers also the trials carried out after 1975 and gives references to other recent literature instead of referring to 3-decade-old articles that have been shown to be erroneous 1 decade ago.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19203652>

Mainardi T, Kapoor S, Bielory L. Complementary and alternative medicine: herbs, phytochemicals and vitamins and their immunologic effects. *J Allergy Clin Immunol.* 2009

32. Hemilä H. **Spectacular reduction in the mortality of acutely injured patients by the administration of vitamins C and E and selenium.** *JPEN J Parenter Enteral Nutr.* 2009;33(4):447-8.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19229041>

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0148607108328520>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/16985>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/242531792>

it seems that Collier and colleagues' calculation of the number needed to treat (NNT) is incorrect. The NNT is the inverse of the risk difference (RD) between the compared groups. Their crude data give RD = 2.34% (8.46%-6.11%), which gives NNT = 42.7 (1/0.0234). Furthermore, if we assume that their adjusted odds ratio is a valid estimate of the risk ratio, we can calculate that the adjusted mortality rate of the antioxidant cohort would be 2.70% (0.32 × 8.46%). With this approach we get NNT = 17.4; that is, 17 patients need to be treated to prevent 1 death. These NNT values are magnitudes lower than the NNT = 1710 calculated by Collier *et al.*

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18596309>

Collier BR, Giladi A, Dossett LA, Dyer L, Fleming SB, Cotton BA. Impact of high-dose antioxidants on outcomes in acutely injured patients. *JPEN J Parenter Enteral Nutr.* 2008

31. Hemilä H. **Evidence-based medicine and the role of antioxidants in physically stressed people.** *Nutr Rev.* 2009;67(1):61-3.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19146508>

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1753-4887.2008.00134.x>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228068>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/23790555>

... In addition to the two missing vitamin C and common cold trials with participants under physical exertion, Nieman ignores other trials that are relevant when considering the effect of antioxidants on physically stressed people... Thus, in his review, Nieman ignores several antioxidant trials with clinical outcomes and does not describe the quantitative results of the trials he does cite. He thereby hampers the

reader from drawing his or her own conclusions regarding the published findings. Instead, Nieman discusses the effect of antioxidants on laboratory variables such as cytokine levels, even though they are surrogates.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18522619>

Nieman DC. Immunonutrition support for athletes. Nutr Rev. 2008

30. Hemilä H. **Feedback on: Kaur B, Rowe BH, Arnold E. Vitamin C supplementation for asthma.**

Cochrane Database Syst Rev. 2009;(1):CD000993. University of Helsinki Open Repository 2009.

<https://zenodo.org/records/6405776>

<https://zenodo.org/records/10959543>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/296440>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/273224023>

See a continuation of this critique in #39, and the **withdrawal** of the Cochrane review in #40.

See the flaws in Cochrane publication ethics in #59.

*The **Cochrane review** vitamin C for asthma (2009 version) has errors in the extraction of data and in the analysis...*

Thus, three trials included in the review found benefit of vitamin C supplementation against EIB at 5 and 8 minutes after the exercise (Cohen 1997; Schachter 1982), or at the time of maximum fall in FEV1 (Tecklenburg 2007). The three P-values calculated above (0.028, 0.0005, 0.038) can be combined by using the Fisher method (Fisher 1948). The combined P[1-tail] = 0.00007 provides evidence that the effects of vitamin C on EIB in these three trials are not explained by random fluctuations.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19160185>

Kaur B, Rowe BH, Arnold E. Vitamin C supplementation for asthma. Cochrane Database Syst Rev. 2009.

The DOI and PMC links of the PubMed record lead to two different versions of the “same” review, and a third version of the “same” review is available at the University of Helsinki Open Repository, see the background for these versions in #59.

29. Hemilä H. **Commentaries on ‘Vitamin C for preventing and treating the common cold’ with responses from the review author.** Evid Based Child Health: A Cochrane Rev J. 2008;3:723-8.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/ebch.261>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/244785237>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228088>

These are responses to comments challenging the validity of the Cochrane review vitamin C and the common cold (2007).

For example,

Shamseer and Vohra state that we did not mention whether foreign language trials were sought and included. We did not describe selection by language which means that we selected trials independent of their language. The reference section of our review shows that we found and assessed trials published in Finnish, German, Spanish and Swedish.

Shamseer and Vohra argue that we should have constructed a funnel plot to explore the possibility of publication bias. Funnel plot has been popular; however, it is not a valid method. For example, different metrics lead to different shapes of the funnel plot. Furthermore, asymmetry can arise from biological heterogeneity so that asymmetry is no evidence of publication bias. Because of various problems, the use of the funnel plot has been strongly discouraged (8). In fact, our Cochrane review serves as a good example against the funnel plot. The six trials with participants under heavy acute physical stress, which found that vitamin C halved the number of colds, are all small. In a funnel plot of all 30 trials measuring incidence, these six small trials would lead to asymmetry. Thus, the funnel plot would “explain” the positive findings by publication bias, which would discourage further trials. In contrast, our subgroup analysis in which the positive results are explained by the special participants and conditions suggests direction for further research to test a justified hypothesis.

Bax et al. claim that in our Cochrane review “there is no information on the geographic locations of the trials.” However, our table “Characteristics of included studies” describes for each included trial the country in which the trial was carried out (1).

Although Bax et al.’s advice to give children kiwi as a source of vitamin C is a pleasant ending to their commentary, evidence and consideration of cost effectiveness should be required for such an advice, too. One gram of vitamin C cost pennies, but corresponds to some half kilograms of kiwi (about 200 mg vitamin C/100 g fruit) which has a substantially higher cost. Thus, if we assume that vitamin C is the important substance in the kiwi fruit, it is much more cost effective to use pure vitamin C. Moreover, if we assume that it is not vitamin C that is beneficial in kiwi, then we should require evidence indicating that kiwi in general is effective for some health outcome.

28. Hemilä H. **Assessment of the importance of double-blinding should be based on systematic reviews: A rebuttal.** J Thromb Haemost. 2008 Jul;6(7):1247-8; author reply 1248-9.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18466312>

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1538-7836.2008.03006.x>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228091>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/25297>

In their paper discussing the importance of double-blinding in controlled trials, Furberg and Soliman stated that “one of the established and fundamental principles for avoiding the problem of bias is to keep the study participants and the investigators blinded, or masked, to the identity of the assigned interventions” [1]. As a support to this argument they described the subgroup findings of **Karlowski et al.’s trial**, which examined the effect of vitamin C supplementation on the common cold [2,3].

Furberg and Soliman put a great weight on the importance of double-blinding, yet they are lax on other fundamental principles of controlled trials. A popular textbook of clinical trials emphasizes that “excluding randomized participants from analysis and subgrouping on the basis of outcome or response variables can lead to biased results of unknown magnitude” [4, p. 284]. The subgroup analysis by **Karlowski et al.** [2,3] violates both of these principles...

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18021306>

Furberg CD, Soliman EZ. Double-blindness protects scientific validity.

J Thromb Haemost. 2008 Feb;6(2):230-1.

27. Hemilä H. **Re: “Bias in clinical intervention research”.**

Am J Epidemiol. 2007 May 15;165(10):1219; author reply 1219-20.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17426041>

<https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwm081>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/240921>

In her Journal review discussing the potential biases of controlled trials, Gluud stated that “[t]he purpose of blinding is to prevent bias associated with patients’ and investigators’ expectations. If interventions are compared with no intervention, an identical placebo may be used. The compared interventions must be identical in taste, smell, appearance, and mode of administration. Any difference may destroy the blinding” (1, p. 496).

The last sentence of this quotation was based on three references, two of them focusing on vitamin C and common cold trials (2, 3). However, **the Karlowski et al. trial (2) and the Chalmers review (3) were both shown to be erroneous a decade ago** (4–6). For example, Karlowski et al. did not mention that 42 percent of the recorded common cold episodes were missing from their subgroup analysis that was the basis for their proposal that “the effects [of vitamin C] demonstrated might be explained equally well by a break in the double blind” (2, p. 1038). In the concurrent review, Karlowski et al.’s subgroup analysis led to a proposal that, in general, “the effects of ascorbic acid [vitamin C] on [common cold] symptoms are the result of the power of suggestion” (3, p. 535).

The lack of validity of **Karlowski et al.’s** (2) placebo explanation is important for methodological and biologic reasons. First, the Karlowski et al. trial has been extensively used as an example of “placebo

effect in action”; for example, it was the only original study cited in the CONSORT statement (7) and the Cochrane Handbook (8). Second, Karlowski et al.’s trial and Chalmers’s review (3) are the most frequent citations in medical textbooks when stating that vitamin C is ineffective against the common cold (6), whereas placebo-controlled trials have shown quite consistently that it is effective, even though the practical significance is unsettled (9)...

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16443796>

Gluud LL. Bias in clinical intervention research. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2006 Mar 15;163(6):493-501.

Further discussion of the comments:

<https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwm372> Michael Marmor et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwm374> Hemilä response

26. Hemilä H. **The role of vitamin C in the treatment of the common cold.**

Am Fam Physician. 2007;76(8):1111, 1115.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17992770>

<https://www.aafp.org/pubs/afp/issues/2007/1015/p1111a.html>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225893>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/5853565>

The authors of “Treatment of the Common Cold,” in American Family Physician, stated that vitamin C is not recommended for active treatment of the common cold. Their recommendation was based on a Cochrane review that I coauthored. The Cochrane review was limited to placebo-controlled trials in which at least 0.2 g of vitamin C was used per day. Most of these trials examined vitamin C administration as regular supplementation and provided strong evidence that vitamin C shortens the duration of colds and alleviates its symptoms. Children benefited more than adults. The data also suggested that high doses of vitamin C are more beneficial than low doses.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17323712>

Simasek M, Blandino DA. Treatment of the common cold. *Am Fam Physician*. 2007

25. Hemilä H. **Small trials focusing on surrogate end points may be uninformative.**

Eur J Appl Physiol. 2007;99(6):707-8.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17219167>

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-006-0387-2>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/6582824>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228092>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10250/8080>

Davison and Gleeson motivated their study by noting that heavy exertion or long-duration exercise may increase the incidence of upper respiratory tract infection (URI) and by citing two trials in which vitamin C reduced the risk of URI associated with marathon runs...

In their trial, Davison and Gleeson compared vitamin C and control periods in the same participants exercising with a cycle ergometer and measured changes in the immune system. Such a study focusing on surrogates of infection susceptibility does not yield any information about whether vitamin C supplementation actually affects the risk of URI or more severe respiratory infections—the clinically relevant outcomes—in physically stressed people.

A further major problem of the Davison and Gleeson trial is the very small size (N = 9). In the Pitt and Costrini trial, the number-needed-to-treat (NNT) to prevent one case of pneumonia with vitamin C was 57. The NNT to prevent one case of the common cold with vitamin C was 7 in the Sabiston and Radomski trial, and 10 in the Ritzel trial. Concluding from such NNT values, it is evident that, as a minimum, several dozens of participants are needed at appropriate experimental conditions for a study to analyze whether immune system changes caused by vitamin C supplementation have any correlations with the clinical effects.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16685547>

- Davison G, Gleeson M. The effect of 2 weeks vitamin C supplementation on immunoendocrine responses to 2.5 h cycling exercise in man. *Eur J Appl Physiol*. 2006
24. Hemilä H. **Vitamin C and exercise-induced immunodepression**. *Eur J Clin Nutr*. 2007;61(10):1241-2.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17426740>
<https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.ejcn.1602751>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/237288826>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10250/135144>
Moreira states that further studies are required to provide unequivocal proof of effect by vitamin C, but in our 2004 meta-analysis we already had three additional trials with physically stressed people, all consistent with the 50% benefit... Moreira claims that the risk of excessive intake of vitamin C may outweigh any potential benefits. Several independent reviewers have concluded that essentially all speculations concerning the risks of vitamin C supplementation are unfounded...
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17136044>
 Moreira A, Kekkonen RA, Delgado L, Fonseca J, Korpela R, Haahtela T. Nutritional modulation of exercise-induced immunodepression in athletes: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Eur J Clin Nutr*. 2007
23. Hemilä H. **The effect of nutrition on exercise-induced immunodepression**. *Nutr Rev*. 2006;64(10 Pt 1):476-7.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17063930>
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1753-4887.2006.tb00179.x>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/237288826>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228097>
The effect of nutrition on exercise-induced immunodepression was reviewed by Gleeson... Gleeson commented that self-evaluation of the common cold might have been unreliable in Graat's trial; however, Gwaltney states in a major textbook of infectious diseases that 'the manifestations of the common cold are so typical and familiar that self-diagnosis by the patient is usually correct'...
... A meta-analysis focusing on the effects of vitamin C on the common cold identified six trials with participants under heavy acute physical stress (combined N = 642), and in this group of studies vitamin C reduced the common cold risk by half (RR = 0.50; 95% CI: 0.38-0.66). Four of these trials had marathon runners as participants, the fifth studied Canadian soldiers in a winter exercise, and the sixth studied Swiss schoolchildren in a skiing camp. The Himmelstein trial mentioned by Gleeson is not in conflict with the pooled RR-estimate because it is small and has a wide confidence interval."
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16572599>
 Gleeson M. Can nutrition limit exercise-induced immunodepression? *Nutr Rev*. 2006
22. Hemilä H. **The protective effect of vitamins A and C on endotoxin-induced oxidative renal tissue damage in rats**. *Tohoku J Exp Med*. 2006;208(2):99-100.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16434830>
<https://doi.org/10.1620/tjem.208.99>
For the Vit C and control group we find difference 26.29 μ m (S.E. 0.783), which corresponds to $t(18\text{ df}) = 33.5$ and $p = 10 \exp(-17)$... Thus, Kanter's evidence for the benefit of Vits A and C against rat endotoxemia is substantially stronger than they state in their paper.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15888972>
 Kanter M, Coskun O, Armutcu F, Uz YH, Kizilay G. Protective effects of vitamin C, alone or in combination with vitamin A, on endotoxin-induced oxidative renal tissue damage in rats. *Tohoku J Exp Med*. 2005

21. Hemilä H. **The safety of vitamin C.**

In: Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections? Thesis 2006 p 62-3.

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/20335>

<https://zenodo.org/records/6395596>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/35656439>

Often the benefits of vitamin C observed in randomized double-blind placebo-controlled trials are disregarded, although at the same time authors may exaggerate the potential harm caused by vitamin C even when it is purely anecdotal (e.g., Olson & Hodges 1987; Herbert 1993 [see #2]).

In a casual survey of 20 physician colleagues, Goodwin and Tangum (1998) found that all of them were aware that high-dose vitamin C ingestion can cause kidney stones. Goodwin and Tangum were, however, interested in where this common 'knowledge' comes from and they combed the medical literature without finding any articles in refereed journals reporting instances of high-dose vitamin C causing kidney stones. Review articles cited book chapters that in turn cited abstracts, letters, and other review articles. Goodwin and Tangum concluded that nowhere in the trail of citations was there any fundamental information on whether or how frequently high-dose vitamin C supplementation might lead to kidney stones. The authors simply stated that vitamin C may cause kidney stones, and as proof they cited other authors who had said the same thing. Thus, this description reveals a typical urban legend; a story that is retold, yet no-one confirms that the story is true.

The anecdote of vitamin C and kidney stones is mentioned in a major textbook of pharmacology: "... risks of megadose treatment ... include formation of kidney stones" (Marcus & Coulston 2001)...

When reviewing the health effects of vitamin C, Olson and Hodges (1987) and Herbert (1993) claimed that "Large intakes of vitamin C may reduce insulin production." This statement was based on a paper published in 1946. Levey and Suter (1946)⁹ reported that vitamin C potentiates the diabetogenic action of alloxan in rats, whose blood-sugar level was determined 3 days after injecting alloxan, or alloxan with vitamin C. Hyperglycemia was observed in 50% of the rats treated with alloxan and vitamin C, in contrast to 17% of the rats treated with alloxan alone. Nevertheless, the authors concluded from their own previous work that "ascorbic acid alone does not produce hyperglycemia" (Levey & Suter 1946). Thus, this old experiment with alloxan-treated rats was the basis for Olson and Hodges (1987) and Herbert (1993) to state that large doses of vitamin C alone may reduce insulin production in human subjects.

Olson and Hodges (1987) and Herbert (1993) stated that "Large intakes of vitamin C may interrupt pregnancies." This suggestion was based on a brief Russian paper published in 1964. Twenty women whose menstruation was delayed by 10-15 days were given 6 g/day of vitamin C, and 16 of them started to menstruate within 3 days (Samborskaya & Ferdman 1964).¹⁰ Pauling (1976a) wrote a letter to the authors inquiring whether any actual direct test of pregnancy was carried out, but he received only a copy of the publication by way of reply. Thus, there was no evidence that the women were pregnant to begin with. Possibly the women just had irregular menstruation, yet this report was valid enough for Olson and Hodges (1987) and Herbert (1993) to conclude that vitamin C may cause miscarriages.

9 Levey S, Suter B. Effect of ascorbic acid on diabetogenic action of alloxan.

Proc Soc Exp Biol Med. 1946;63(2):341-3.

<https://zenodo.org/records/19892132>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20277744>

<https://doi.org/10.3181/00379727-63-15595>

10 Samborskaya EP, Ferdman TD. The mechanism of termination of pregnancy by ascorbic acid.

Bulletin of Experimental Biology and Medicine 1966;62:934-5.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00810734>

English summary in the Chemical Abstracts: AN 1966:493662.

<https://zenodo.org/records/19892392>

Olson and Hodges (1987) and Herbert (1993) also argued that “Large intakes of vitamin C may lower plasma vitamin B₁₂ levels.” This claim was originally made by Herbert himself (Herbert & Jacob 1974), however, it was shown afterwards that the apparent breakdown of vitamin B₁₂ was due to methodological shortcomings (Newmark et al. 1979; Marcus 1981), and the vitamin B₁₂ level was not decreased in patients administered as much as 4 g/day of vitamin C for 11 months or more (Afroz et al. 1975), or in children administered gram-doses of vitamin C for years (Ekvall et al. 1981). However, these papers were not cited by Olson and Hodges (1987) or Herbert (1993).¹¹

In extreme cases, suggestions about vitamin C toxicity have been based on double-speculation. Herbert (1993) stated that (1) vitamin C might cause elevated iron levels, and (2) elevated iron levels might cause increased risk of coronary heart disease. However, (1) in order to quantify the effect of vitamin C supplementation on iron status, Cook et al. (1984) administered 2 g/day of vitamin C to 9 subjects for 2 years without finding indications of iron accumulation, and (2) several studies with different types of settings were unable to corroborate the hypothesis that raised iron levels increase the risk of coronary heart disease (Bendich & Langseth 1995; Hemilä & Paunio 1997).

Rivers (1987)¹² reviewed 74 publications dealing with the possible toxicity of vitamin C and concluded that “Large quantities of ascorbic acid will not result in calcium-oxalate stones, increased uric acid excretion, impaired vitamin B₁₂ status, iron overload, systemic conditioning, or increased mutagenic activity in healthy individuals.” In another review, Marks (1989)¹³ concluded that “A large number of adverse reactions have been alleged to occur with the use of large doses of ascorbic acid, but almost without exception further study has demonstrated that the allegations are without foundation ... an overview of all the information shows that the safe daily level is at least 100 times the RDA.” The RDA level for vitamin C was 60 mg/day at that time. Hathcock (1997)¹⁴ stated that “Many hypothetical adverse effects of high intakes of vitamin C have been cited for decades. Most, with the exception of mild and transient gastrointestinal effects, seem to have little or no known factual basis.” Several other reviews have also concluded that vitamin C is safe in doses around 1 g/day (Hanck 1982,¹⁵...

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/3565296>

Olson JA, Hodges RE. Recommended dietary intakes (RDI) of vitamin C in humans. Am J Clin Nutr. 1987

11 A short summary of the speculation on harms of vitamin C on vitamin B₁₂:

“In 1974, JAMA published a study by Herbert and Jacobs that claimed that vitamin C causes the breakdown of vitamin B₁₂. Pauling described the subsequent chain of events as follows: ‘When Newmark and his coworkers found that the claim could not be substantiated, and that in fact vitamin C does not destroy the vitamin B₁₂ in the food, they sent their paper to the editor of JAMA, which seems clearly to be the place where the correction should be published. He held it for half a year, and then refused to publish it, thus delaying its publication in another journal and preventing many of the readers of the original article by Herbert and Jacobs from learning that their results were incorrect. These actions suggest that the AMA works to protect American physicians from information that runs counter to its own prejudices. The evidence indicates that the AMA is prejudiced against vitamin C’. In 1976, Newmark’s study was published in a smaller journal, which does not reach the wide readership of JAMA. Five years after the publication of the Herbert and Jacobs’ vitamin B₁₂ paper, JAMA finally published a short paper by Newmark discussing the flaws in Herbert’s study. Thus, for five years the readers of JAMA were misled that vitamin C causes breakdown of vitamin B₁₂. There is no evidence of this, and ‘results of in vivo studies in human subjects have shown that vitamin C intakes up to 4 g/day did not induce vitamin B₁₂ deficiency’.”

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35054455> p.23-24.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/life12010062>

12 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/3304071>

13 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20382016>

14 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9250127>

15 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20381351>

20. Hemilä H. **Problems with statements by experts.**

In: Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections? 2006 p 63-6.

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/20335>

The status of an ‘expert’ implies that an individual is thoroughly familiar with the particular field. Unfortunately, in the vitamin C field, the track record of many experts is poor...

The review of vitamin C by Olson and Hodges (1987), which contained the anecdotal stories of vitamin C toxicity (see the previous section), was planned as the vitamin C section of the 10th edition of the RDA recommendations (Olson 1986; Pellett 1988). The US National Academy of Sciences decided, however, not to publish the RDA draft by the first committee because of an impasse resulting from scientific differences of opinion between the first committee and the scientific reviewers appointed by the National Academy of Sciences (Press 1985; Marshall 1985)...

Victor Herbert, who reiterated the anecdotal stories of vitamin C toxicity (see the previous section) in one of his papers (Herbert 1993) [see #2], was also a member of the committee preparing the 9th edition of the US RDA nutritional recommendations (FNB 1980)... In his reminiscences Pauling described an acrimonious exchange of letters with Victor Herbert who rejected the results of all placebo-controlled trials on vitamin C and the common cold without any reasonable argument. Pauling commented that “I finally became sufficiently irritated by this fellow that I decided I ought to do something about it. So I sat down one summer and in two months wrote a book, Vitamin C and the Common Cold” (Marinacci 1995 pp 248-51).¹⁶ In this respect Herbert was, paradoxically, indirectly behind the increase in the popular enthusiasm for vitamin C supplementation that resulted from Pauling’s book...

Thomas Chalmers, Paul Meier, A. Steward Truswell, and Jos Kleijnen are experts in controlled trials, medical statistics, nutrition, and systematic reviews, yet their reviews on vitamin C and the common cold contain lots of factual errors and misleading statements (see pp 36-45). The Chalmers (1975) and Dykes and Meier (1975) reviews¹⁷ were cited in major textbooks of infectious diseases and in the US RDA recommendations, although some of the numerous shortcomings of both reviews should have been apparent to any expert even superficially familiar with the original study reports.

In the most recent US nutritional recommendations (FNB 2000 pp 126-7),¹⁸ Chalmers’ review (1975) and the Hemilä and Herman criticism (1995) [#4] of Chalmers’ review are cited in the same paragraph without mentioning that the latter paper shows that the former review is invalid. Thus, the experts writing the vitamin C chapter did not read or understand the two papers cited to see that they were incompatible.

16 Linus Pauling's reason for writing “Vitamin C and the Common Cold”
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20343221>

17 **US RDA. Recommended Dietary Allowances 1989**

<https://doi.org/10.17226/1349>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK234924>

<https://www.nationalacademies.org/publications/1349>

“Several reviewers (**Chalmers, 1975; Dykes and Meier, 1975**) have concluded that any benefits of large doses of ascorbic acid for these conditions are too small to justify recommending routine intake of large amounts by the entire population.” p.120.

18 Institute of Medicine (2000) Vitamin C. in: Dietary Reference Intakes for Vitamin C, Vitamin E, Selenium and Carotenoids, pp. 95-185. Washington DC: National Academies Press. p.126-7

“Common Cold: There has been a great deal of interest in the use of vitamin C to protect against the common cold, much of this research stimulated by the views put forth by the late Linus Pauling (**Hemila and Herman, 1995**). Reviews of numerous studies generally conclude that vitamin C megadoses have no significant effect on incidence of the common cold, but do provide a moderate benefit in terms of the duration and severity of episodes in some groups (**Chalmers, 1975 ...**”

<https://doi.org/10.17226/9810>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25077263>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK225480>

<https://nap.nationalacademies.org/read/9810/chapter/7>

19. Hemilä H. **The most influential trial on vitamin C and the common cold;**¹⁹
The conclusions of the Karlowski et al trial (1975).

In: Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections? 2006 p 21-7, 59-60

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/20335>

See a detailed critique in #5 and #6.

In the middle of the 1970s, Karlowski, Chalmers, et al. (1975) published a vitamin C common cold trial which received widespread attention for several reasons. First, the trial was carried out at the NIH. Since the participants in the trial were NIH employees, the social background of this particular trial was highly significant. Secondly, the principal investigator of the trial was Thomas Chalmers, who was an eminent clinical trialist (see p 36) [see #4, #17, #41, footnote 21]. Third, the trial was published in JAMA, a respected journal with a particularly wide circulation. Finally, the same issue of JAMA contained a review of vitamin C and the common cold, which concluded that it has no effects on colds (Dykes & Meier 1975; see pp 42-5) [see #15]....

The re-analysis of the Karlowski trial (I) was criticized by Thomas Chalmers (1996), but the criticism seems not to be valid (I; Hemilä 1996c) [see #6], except for Chalmers' statement that they used capsules in their trial, and not tablets as erroneously stated in Paper I...

The Karlowski et al. (1975) trial is by far the most influential of the trials on vitamin C and the common cold (Table 10). Karlowski et al. concluded that the apparent benefit of vitamin C in their double-blind placebo-controlled trial was explained, paradoxically, by the placebo effect. In this thesis it is shown that the 'placebo effect' explanation is inconsistent with Karlowski's own data (Paper I; see p 25).

Karlowski et al. (1975) considered that the effect, even if real, has no clinical importance, and concluded that "It does not seem worthwhile to take two capsules or tablets three times a day for the rest of one's life to achieve such a small and equivocal benefit." In this conclusion, they missed several important findings in their own trial, which are discussed above. First, they could have noted that three times a day during a cold episode is much more feasible and much less expensive than 'three times a day for the rest of one's life,' and their own results indicated that the effect of therapeutic supplementation may be even greater than that of regular supplementation. Second, as there was a linear dose-dependency in their own results, they could have noted that therapeutic doses larger than 6 g/day might have decreased the duration of episodes by over 17%. Third, since they cited the Anderson et al. paper (1972), reporting that vitamin C supplementation is much more beneficial for subjects with low fruit juice intake, they could have noted that their own subjects were probably not the kind of people that would derive the greatest benefit from vitamin C supplementation. It would seem more relevant to ask what the subgroups that would benefit most from vitamin C supplementation are, rather than to ask whether a fixed numerical value found with NIH employees is great enough to validate regular vitamin C supplementation for the general population.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/163386>

Karlowski TR, Chalmers TC, Frenkel LD, Kapikian AZ, Lewis TL, Lynch JM.

Ascorbic acid for the common cold. A prophylactic and therapeutic trial. JAMA. 1975

19 **Selected list of papers that cite the Karlowski (1975) trial**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20204507>

See also Tables 1 and 2 in:

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35054455>

A Google Scholar search identified 363 citations to the Karlowski (1975) trial by 2026-5.

18. Hemilä H. **Pauling's meta-analyses (1971a,b).**²⁰

In: Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections? 2006 p 35-6.

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/20335>

In his first meta-analysis in the Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, Linus Pauling analyzed the findings of 4 placebo-controlled trials in which at least 0.1 g/day of vitamin C was administered regularly to the study group (1971a). In his second meta-analysis in the American Journal of Clinical Nutrition, Pauling focused on the best 2 of the 4 trials (1971b; Cowan et al. 1942; Ritzel 1961; Table 3).

Among the 4 trials included in Pauling's meta-analysis (1971a; see Pauling 1972; p 28), the largest dose was used by Ritzel (1961), and Pauling based his quantitative estimations on this trial. Ritzel found that the common cold symptoms in the vitamin C group were 31% shorter and the number of colds 45% lower in the vitamin C group. Pauling also calculated the combination of duration and incidence, 'integrated morbidity' referring to the total sickness days per person during the trial, and this was reduced by 61% in the Ritzel trial (Table 3). Pauling (1971a) then modeled the dose-dependency of vitamin C effect with exponential formulas for which he took constants from the Ritzel trial. Pauling assumed that the main problem in his estimation was inaccuracy caused by 'experimental error,' although he did note that "The values are, of course, expected to depend somewhat on the nature of the population and environment." However, even with these explicit reservations he was far too optimistic. He could not imagine how great the variations in the results would be in the forthcoming trials. Neither did he consider the possibility that the effects observed by Ritzel may have been caused at least in part by low dietary vitamin C intake, in which case a smaller dose might have produced a similar benefit, and in such a case modeling the vitamin C effect as a function of the supplementary dose would be completely erroneous...

Pauling (1971a,b) put much weight on the 'integrated morbidity' outcome and summarized the findings of trials by this outcome in his later texts as well. This measure led Pauling to adhere strongly to the idea of regular supplementation. However, this is not a good combined measure, since the effects on incidence and duration/severity have quite different patterns (Fig. 3), and it is thus more to the point to analyze these two outcomes separately... Pauling was qualitatively correct in his conclusion that vitamin C does affect the duration and severity of colds, and probably the incidence of colds in certain specific conditions, but he was greatly over-optimistic... As regards the errors in Pauling's quantitative conclusions, it should obviously be taken into account that essentially all of the trials available today were carried out after Pauling worked on the topic and, even more importantly, were carried out precisely because Pauling popularized the topic (Fig. 2).

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4941984>

Pauling L. The significance of the evidence about ascorbic acid and the common cold. Proc Natl Acad Sci USA. 1971

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4940368>

Pauling L. Ascorbic acid and the common cold. Am J Clin Nutr. 1971

20 **Linus Pauling, chemist.**

Linus Pauling's texts on vitamin C and the common cold, and biographies of Pauling:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20374066>

17. Hemilä H. **Chalmers' meta-analysis (1975).**²¹

In: Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections? 2006 p 36-8.

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/20335>

See a detailed critique in #4, see also #43.

Thomas Chalmers was an eminent pioneer in controlled trials, and one of the early promoters of meta-analysis... Chalmers' meta-analysis was cited in several major reviews of common cold therapy ... in stating that vitamin C is useless for colds.

Chalmers' meta-analysis was recently shown to contain a large number of serious errors (Hemilä & Herman 1995). In some cases the data was inconsistent with the original published data, there were errors in calculation, the selection of trials was not consistent, and in some trials a clinically less meaningful outcome was selected...

Chalmers did not consider the dose of vitamin C used in the trials. At the extreme, Karlowski et al. (1975) administered up to 6 g/day of vitamin C to their subjects, whereas Cowan et al. (1942) administered 25 mg/day as their lowest supplementary dose (Table 12), meaning an up to 240-fold difference between the lowest and highest vitamin C doses used; however, these two trials were presented side-by-side by Chalmers (1975) in his table without noting this difference (Table 14)

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1092164>

Chalmers TC. Effects of ascorbic acid on the common cold. An evaluation of the evidence.

Am J Med. 1975

21 **The Chalmers review has been extensively cited in journal articles and textbooks, see Table 3 in:**

<https://doi.org/10.3390/life12010062>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc8779885>

For example,

US RDA. Recommended Dietary Allowances 1989

<https://doi.org/10.17226/1349>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK234924>

“Several reviewers (**Chalmers, 1975**; Dykes and Meier, 1975) have concluded that any benefits of large doses of ascorbic acid for these conditions are too small to justify recommending routine intake of large amounts by the entire population.” p.120.

Major citations to the reviews on vitamin C and the common cold by Chalmers (1975) and by Dykes and Meier (1975).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20344539>

Thomas Chalmers, clinical trialist.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thomas_C._Chalmers

<https://www.nytimes.com/1995/12/29/nyregion/dr-thomas-c-chalmers-a-president-of-mt-sinai-dies-at-78.html>

<https://www.jameslindlibrary.org/articles/thomas-c-chalmers-1917-1995>

<https://circulatingnow.nlm.nih.gov/2014/12/18/thomas-c-chalmers-clinical-research-pragmatist>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2878827>

David Sackett describes in this paper that Thomas Chalmers' 1955 clinical trial report changed his career and led to the emergence of **the EBM movement**:

<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.g371>

According to **Richard Smith** and **Drummond Rennie**, Thomas Chalmers was one of the “three individuals from an earlier generation [who] were particularly important in inspiring” **the EBM movement**:

<https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-124-7-199604010-00022>

<https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-124-7-199604010-00023>

<https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-124-7-199604010-00024>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1335248>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1335469>

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(96\)90369-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(96)90369-4)

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1996.03540080078041>

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0197-2456\(96\)90026-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0197-2456(96)90026-4)

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0197-2456\(97\)82189-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0197-2456(97)82189-7)

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0141076815586354>

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0141076815606279>

16. Hemilä H. **Kleijnen's meta-analysis (1989).**²²

In: Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections? 2006 p 38-40.

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/20335>

Kleijnen et al. (1989) carried out a thorough search of the literature on vitamin C and the common cold and published a biography of the controlled trials identified. Only a few old trials are missing from Kleijnen's bibliography, and a few have been published since (Table 6)...

Kleijnen excluded 27 placebo-controlled trials from further analysis because they got low 'Kleijnen scores' in the arbitrary scoring system (listed in Table 17). Overall these trials contain 8,579 common cold episodes, thus nearly as many as the 'high score trials.' 11 of the trials excluded are randomized and double-blind trials recording 3,740 common cold episodes (Table 17). Kleijnen thus excluded a large number of randomized and double-blind trials from his further analysis, but included the Coulehan trial (1974) that was non-randomized and the Anderson trial (1974) which had evidence of various problems. Although the number of episodes is highly relevant to the precision of the results, Kleijnen included 2 trials that had less than 100 episodes (Table 15) but excluded 7 randomized double-blind placebo controlled trials that had over 100 episodes (Table 17). The final sets of included and excluded trials in Kleijnen's review are good examples of the problems that result from mechanical 'quality scoring.'

Furthermore, Kleijnen shows the 11 'high scoring' trials in a table with subjective comments, but the presentation suffers from several shortcomings (Table 18). The subjective comments are also in some cases demonstrably erroneous. Kleijnen states that Pitt and Costrini (1979) found 'no difference' in the severity of colds between the study groups. In fact, they reported an average severity score of 1.87 in the vitamin C group and 1.97 in the placebo group and tested the difference: χ^2 (15 df) = 27.8 (P = 0.012). Although a 5% difference in severity is a clinically minor finding, the statistically significant difference suggests a real biological effect. It is possible that this effect is greater under dissimilar conditions and in this respect a subjective comment of 'no difference' is misleading.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20159299>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2677773>

<https://www.ntvg.nl/artikelen/vitamine-c-en-verkoudheid-overzicht-van-een-megadosis-literatuur>

Kleijnen J, ter Riet G, Knipschild PG. Vitamine C en verkoudheid; overzicht van een megadosis literatuur; Vitamin C and the common cold; review of a megadosis literature.

Ned Tijdschr Geneeskd. 1989;133(31):1532-5.

22 **Jos Kleijnen, systematic reviewer.**

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=0sporvgAAAAJ>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/20335> p 38:

Kleijnen's meta-analysis (1989) was published in Dutch with a translation into English in his thesis.

This meta-analysis is of particular interest since Kleijnen became the director of the Centre for Reviews and Dissemination (CRD, York, UK) which writes abstracts of meta-analyses for the Database of Abstracts of Reviews of Effectiveness (DARE).

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK285222>

Prior to joining CRD Kleijnen was the Director of the Dutch Cochrane Centre. Also, Kleijnen is one of the authors of the book entitled Systematic Reviews to Support Evidence-Based Medicine (Khan et al. 2003).

Furthermore, Kleijnen's 1989 meta-analysis of vitamin C and the common cold was used as an example in a paper on systematic reviews in BMJ (Knipschild 1994),

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/7950526>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/29724801>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/15247765>

which was later republished as part of a book (Ian Chalmers & Altman 1995 pp 9-16).

<https://www.jameslindlibrary.org/chalmers-i-altman-dg-1995>

<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.311.7007.759>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2550765>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1055360>

15. Hemilä H. **The Dykes and Meier review (1975).**²³

In: Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections? 2006 p 42-5.

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/20335>

See also critique in #7.

For example,

In 1975 JAMA published a review of vitamin C and the common cold by Michael Dykes and Paul Meier in the same issue as the Karlowski et al. trial (1975). Meier is an eminent statistician, the second author of the widely used Kaplan-Meier survival analysis method (1958), and he was elected statistician of the year in the USA in 1985 (ASA 2005). This review in a wide circulation medical journal has thus been highly influential... The Dykes and Meier review (1975) contains several shortcomings (Hemilä 1996a)...

Dykes and Meier (1975) presented the results of the Anderson et al. trial (1972), but did not calculate any estimates of effect, such as percentage difference in favor of the vitamin C group, which hampers the reader in considering the practical significance of the findings. Dykes and Meier wrote of the Anderson 1972 trial: "The estimated effect is considerably less than that predicted by Pauling for the dose level." Anderson had reported a 30% decrease ($P = 0.000,5$) in the 'total number of days confined to house' per participant. Dykes and Meier's comment seems irrelevant as many readers might consider that with an inexpensive nutrient which costs pennies per gram and is safe in large doses, even such moderate benefits might be worthy of exploitation irrespective of how they compare with Pauling's predictions.

Pauling (1976b) considered that "some significant studies in this field were not mentioned by Dykes and Meier, and some important aspects of the studies discussed by them were also not mentioned by them." Pauling thus wrote a manuscript in which he presented the results of the relevant studies, his own interpretations, and some criticism of Dykes and Meier's argument...

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1089817>

Dykes MH, Meier P. Ascorbic acid and the common cold. Evaluation of its efficacy and toxicity. JAMA 1975 Mar 10;231(10):1073-9.

23 **The Dykes and Meier review has been extensively cited in articles and textbooks, see Table 3 in:**

<https://doi.org/10.3390/life12010062>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc8779885>

For example,

US RDA. Recommended Dietary Allowances 1989

<https://doi.org/10.17226/1349>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK234924>

"Several reviewers (Chalmers, 1975; Dykes and Meier, 1975) have concluded that any benefits of large doses of ascorbic acid for these conditions are too small to justify recommending routine intake of large amounts by the entire population." p.120.

Major citations to the reviews on vitamin C and the common cold by Chalmers (1975) and by Dykes and Meier (1975).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20344539>

See Linus Pauling's (1976) criticism of the Michael Dykes and Paul Meier (1975) review:

Pauling L (1976) Ascorbic acid and the common cold: evaluation of its efficacy and toxicity. Part I. Medical Tribune 17(12):18-9.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11546757>

Pauling L (1976) Ascorbic acid and the common cold. Part II. Medical Tribune 17(13):37-8.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11547088>

Paul Meier, statistician.

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Paul_Meier_\(statistician\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Paul_Meier_(statistician))

<https://doi.org/10.1191%2F1740774504cn011xx>

[https://doi.org/10.1016%2F0140-6736\(11\)61438-4](https://doi.org/10.1016%2F0140-6736(11)61438-4)

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3477951>

14. Hemilä H. **Truswell's mini-review (1986).**²⁴

In: Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections? 2006 p 45.

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/20335>

See also critique in #7.

A. Steward Truswell is an eminent nutritionist who was a co-editor of a major textbook of nutrition (Davidson et al. 1975, 1979), and the author of a popular book ABC of Nutrition, which is currently printed as the fourth edition (Truswell 2003). Truswell (1986) reviewed the vitamin C trials in a letter to the New England Journal of Medicine. The main text of the letter was only half a column long, but a journal with great prestige and a wide circulation makes the statements in Truswell's mini-review influential and worthy of a critical look. This mini-review was cited in Truswell's own book on nutrition (2003 p 64) as the only reference to the topic of vitamin C and the common cold...

Truswell did not present any figures or P-values of the original reports, merely providing subjective comments about the trials. Neither did he make any effort to rationalize the great variations in the reported results. For example, on pharmacological grounds it is highly plausible that the effect depends on the dose. Truswell, however, listed the Karlowski et al. trial (1975) in which vitamin C dose was up to 6 g/day and the Dahlberg et al. trial (1944) in which the dose was only 0.05 g/day side-by-side without mentioning that there was a 120-fold discrepancy in vitamin C dosage. Obviously, such trials are not equivalent.

At the end of his mini-review, Truswell stated that "In another five combined trials there appeared to be slight amelioration of symptoms, which was not statistically significant." In fact, the 5 papers cited by Truswell contained 6 trials and not 5 (Table 21; Hemilä 1996a). Furthermore, all 6 trials reported a statistically significant benefit in at least one of the outcomes (Table 21). Thus Truswell's statement is gravely misleading, even though the 5 papers did contain some other outcomes in which the benefit was not significant statistically. Some further problems in Truswell's minireview are discussed elsewhere (Hemilä 1996a).

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM198609113151113>

Truswell AS. Ascorbic Acid [letter]. N Engl J Med 1986;315:708-10.

24 **Arthur Stewart Truswell, nutritionist.**

<https://archives-search.sydney.edu.au/nodes/view/141780>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Arthur-Truswell>

He is a co-author of a widely used book:

<https://doi.org/10.1093/hesc/9780198866671.001.0001>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379554737>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6020736>

<https://doi.org/10.1071/HC12175>

<https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/78.3.499>

<https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.ejcn.1600820>

https://archive.org/details/essentialsofhumana0000unse_k9a4

13. Hemilä H. **Analysis of clinical data with breached blindness.**

Stat Med. 2006 Apr 30;25(8):1434-7; author reply 1437-8.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.2347>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228098>

...

The other trial Chow and Shao cited focused on the effects of vitamin C on the common cold. **The Karlowski et al. trial** lasted for 9 months and used 4 treatment arms [7], not 2 as stated by Chow and Shao [1]. Each participant received 2 kinds of capsule: prophylactic (each day over the trial) and therapeutic (5 days during a cold). Ascorbic acid (3 g/day) was used in the vitamin C capsules and lactose in the placebo capsules, a different combination being administered to each arm so that 3+3 g/day was the largest dose. Since lactose is sweet whereas ascorbic acid is acidic, some participants apparently inferred their treatment by taste. After the Karlowski trial was concluded, the participants were asked using a questionnaire which capsules they thought they had been administered. There was strong bias in favour of correct answers in the case of prophylactic capsules ($P < 10^{-6}$), but not in the case of therapeutic capsules ($P = 0.3$). After this puzzling finding, Karlowski carried out a subgroup analysis by dividing participants into those who remained 'blinded' (guessed incorrectly) and those who became 'unblinded' (guessed correctly) during the trial. In this analysis, all the benefit of vitamin C was restricted to the 'unblinded' participants, whereas no differences were observed in the 'blinded' participants. Thus, Karlowski concluded that 'the effects demonstrated might be explained equally well by a break in the double blind' [7]. Because the trial was initiated as double-blind, this was such a spectacular conclusion that the Karlowski trial has been cited as an example of the placebo effect in action by numerous clinical trialists including Chow and Shao [1] and the CONSORT group [8].

However, the data reported are inconsistent with **Karlowski's** 'placebo explanation.' Some 11 participants answered the type of therapeutic capsule correctly and some 56 the prophylactic capsule [9]. Thus, assuming that the results are explained by the placebo effect, we would expect the prophylactic capsules to be substantially more effective than the therapeutic capsules. However, the prophylactic capsules were 34 per cent less effective than the therapeutic capsules in all study participants (reduction in cold duration by -0.48 and -0.73 days per episode) and 75 per cent less effective in 'unblinded' participants (-0.75 and -3.0 days) [9]. The greater benefit from the therapeutic capsules is inconsistent with Karlowski's 'placebo explanation,' since there is no valid evidence that any participants inferred their therapeutic capsules ($P = 0.3$) and, at most, only some 8 per cent did [9].

Furthermore, **Karlowski et al.** did not describe how they divided their participants into the 'blinded' and 'unblinded' subgroups. The two subgroups were treated as if they were complementary, yet their sum does not equal all participants. In total, there were 105 common cold episodes (42 per cent of all colds) missing from Karlowski's subgroup analysis [9]. The maximum effect of vitamin C on common cold duration in the 'missing group' was even greater (-1.4 days; 6 vs 0 g/day [9]) than the maximum effect across the whole study population (-1.22 days). Karlowski et al. did not mention the exclusion of the 105 episodes from their subgroup analysis, nor did they offer a rationalization for the greater than average benefit among the participants who were neither 'blinded' nor 'unblinded.' There are a number of further logical inconsistencies with Karlowski's 'placebo explanation' [9]. The re-analysis of the Karlowski et al. trial was commented on but no valid counter-arguments were presented [10, 11].

There has been a long-lasting popular belief that vitamin C is beneficial against the common cold and subjective observation may thus affect the inference of treatment.

In fact, **the ‘inference from subjective observation’ concept was directly supported by the parallel report of the Karlowski trial [12].**²⁵ Among participants who had not tasted their prophylactic placebo capsules, those who had colds during the trial tended to suspect they were being given placebo (15 of 18 participants), whereas those who did not have colds tended to suspect vitamin C (6 of 8 participants) (Fisher- $P = 0.02$). Evidently, a similar inference applies to the duration of colds, but this was not considered by Karlowski. In placebo-controlled trials vitamin C has reduced the duration and severity of colds up to 20–50 per cent [13, 14] so that some people may correctly infer from subjective observation whether they received vitamin C or placebo. In such a case it is inappropriate to ‘adjust’ the results for ‘breached blindness’ because correct identification may be caused by the physiological effects...

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15083477>

Chow SC, Shao J. Analysis of clinical data with breached blindness. *Stat Med.* 2004 Apr 30;23(8):1185-93.

12. Hemilä H. **Echinacea, vitamin C, the common cold, and blinding.** *Clin Infect Dis.* 2005;41(5):762-3.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16080106>

<https://doi.org/10.1086/432629>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/253841>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/7680103>

... To support this suggestion, they referred to an old review on vitamin C and the common cold [4] by commenting that the author, **Chalmers**, “described a study that initially showed a positive therapeutic effect of capsules containing vitamin C on the common cold. However, blinding was not maintained, because many subjects bit through the capsules to taste the contents, which they correctly identified. When data from the unblinded subjects were discarded, ‘there were no differences in the durations of colds’ [p. 534]” [1, p. 810]. The Chalmers review [4] was shown to be erroneous a decade ago; it has data inconsistent with the original study publications, errors in calculations, and other problems [5, 6]. The particular trial referred to by Chalmers [4] was undertaken by **Karlowski et al.** [7]. It was initiated as a double-blind, placebo-controlled trial, but, after the trial, several participants correctly guessed their treatment, and this led Karlowski to carry out a subgroup analysis according to “correct” and “incorrect” guessing. In this analysis, the benefit of vitamin C was restricted to participants with “correct” guesses. Thus Karlowski concluded that “the effects demonstrated might be explained equally well by a break in the double blind” [7, p. 1038]. Because of such spectacular findings in this subgroup analysis, the Karlowski trial has often been cited as an example of the placebo effect in action. However, the subgroup analysis excluded 105 episodes of common cold (42% of all episodes of cold), even though the 2 subgroups were presented as if they were complementary [8]. There are numerous additional problems with Karlowski’s placebo effect explanation, and, consequently, it is not a valid interpretation to the study results [8]. Furthermore, a recent meta-analysis of trials comparing placebo and no-treatment groups with respect to diverse medical topics found no or minimal evidence for the placebo effect, which indicates that it is not as large as commonly assumed [9].

... Even though more studies are needed to evaluate the practical importance of vitamin C supplementation on colds, **the Chalmers review [4] and the Karlowski trial [7]** should not be cited as evidence that the effects of vitamin C are explained by the placebo effect. Also, the Karlowski trial should not be used as a basis to propose the placebo-effect explanation for other potential treatments for the common cold [1].

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15736012>

Caruso TJ, Gwaltney JM Jr. Treatment of the common cold with echinacea: a structured review. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2005

25 Lewis TL, Karlowski TR, Kapikian AZ, Lynch JM, Shaffer GW, George DA. A controlled clinical trial of ascorbic acid for the common cold. *Ann N Y Acad Sci.* 1975;258:505-12. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1106302>

11. Hemilä H. **Allocation concealment and blinding: when ignorance is bliss.**

Med J Aust. 2005 Aug 1;183(3):165-6; author reply 166.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16175687>

<https://doi.org/10.5694/j.1326-5377.2005.tb06975.x>

In their article on controlled trials, Forder et al described **the trial by Karlowski et al on vitamin C and the common cold** as an example of how patients' or investigators' preconceptions about the value of the treatment may affect a trial's results. However, their presentation of this trial is misleading in two respects.

Firstly, the **Karlowski et al** trial was reanalysed and the "placebo-effect explanation" of the original authors was shown to be erroneous. For example, their subgroup analysis of "blinded" and "non-blinded" participants excluded 42% of all episodes of colds, even though the subgroups were presented as complementary; numerous further problems are detailed elsewhere. Thus, the trial by Karlowski and colleagues cannot be seen as an example of the placebo effect in action...

Secondly, the trial by **Karlowski et al** was focused on the effect of vitamin C on the common cold, and thus the "placebo effect explanation" in this particularly influential trial is crucial to the biological question. A recent meta-analysis of 55 placebo-controlled trials found that regular vitamin C supplementation had no effect on the incidence of colds in the general population (relative risk [RR], 0.98; 95% CI, 0.95–1.00), but reduced the incidence of colds in people exposed to substantial physical or cold stress (RR, 0.50; 95% CI, 0.38–0.66). Also, regular vitamin C intake reduced the duration of colds in adults by 8% (95% CI, 3%–13%) and in children by 13.5% (95% CI, 5%–21%). Although further studies are needed to evaluate the practical significance of these findings, it is evident that the interpretation by Karlowski and colleagues that the effect of vitamin C on the common cold may be explained by the break in the double blind is false and should not be reiterated.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15651970>

Forder PM, Gebski VJ, Keech AC. Allocation concealment and blinding: when ignorance is bliss. Med J Aust. 2005 Jan 17;182(2):87-9.

10. Hemilä H. **Assessment of blinding may be inappropriate after the trial.**

Contemp Clin Trials. 2005 Aug;26(4):512-4; author reply 514-5.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15951244>

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cct.2005.04.002>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228099>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10250/7981>

In their paper discussing the assessment of blinding in clinical trials, Bang et al. [1] based their analysis on the premise that "all participants randomly guess their assignment... This is the most ideal scenario in reality" ([1], p. 149). However, this premise makes an implicit assumption that the drug does not differ from placebo in any physiological effects that a person could observe subjectively, which is a very strong assumption. If a drug is truly effective, such as penicillin for pneumococcal pneumonia, both the patient and the physician can infer the treatment with high certainty by subjective observations. Thus, when the drug is truly effective, we are expecting "breaking of blindness".

Bang et al. [1] admit in their discussion, that "it is possible that unsuccessful blindness may not influence statistical analysis in the end." Thereafter they state that "in a well-known trial of vitamin C, the perceptions affected the endpoint concerning cold symptoms," thus providing **the Karlowski et al. [2] trial** as the single example of a trial in which breaking of blindness may have caused the observed difference between the study arms.

The **Karlowski** trial was planned as a double-blind placebo-controlled trial. Because of the shortage of time, no appropriate placebo (e.g. citric acid) was manufactured, and they used lactose-placebo, which is sweet and differs in taste from vitamin C (ascorbic acid). At the end of the trial many participants guessed correctly their treatment, and this led Karlowski to carry out a subgroup analysis by the blindness status of the participants. Vitamin C appeared effective among "unblinded" participants, but no effect was seen

among “blinded” participants [2], [3]. This subgroup finding was spectacular by indicating that knowledge of treatment explained the differences between the study arms. Therefore the Karlowski trial has been frequently cited as an example of the importance of blinding, e.g., in the CONSORT statement pointing out the importance of trial quality [4], and as the only example by Bang et al. [1].

However, the subgroup analysis by **Karlowski** et al. [2], [3] is not valid. For example, a total of 249 common cold episodes were recorded in the trial, but the subgroup analysis contained only 144 episodes, so that 105 episodes (42% of all) were missing [5]. Karlowski did not mention the exclusion of 105 episodes from their subgroup analysis, nor did they present their rationalization for the greater than average benefit (sic!) in the excluded participants who were neither “blinded” nor “unblinded” [5]. Further problems of the “placebo effect explanation” are detailed elsewhere [5]. Chalmers, the principal author, commented on the re-analysis of the Karlowski trial [6], but his criticism appears to be invalid [7].

Vitamin C has consistently reduced the duration and severity of colds [8], [9], and some of the largest trials explicitly reported that vitamin C and placebo tablets looked and tasted the same [10], [11], [12]. The validity of the placebo should be determined before the trial. Blindness at the end of the trial may be influenced by the true physiological effects of the drug [5].

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15020033>

Bang H, Ni L, Davis CE. Assessment of blinding in clinical trials. *Control Clin Trials*. 2004 Apr;25(2):143-56.

9. Hemilä H. **Vitamin C intake and susceptibility to the common cold – invited commentaries.**

Br J Nutr. 1997;78(5):857-9; author reply 861-6.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9389907>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/223364>

<https://zenodo.org/records/14610441>

<https://doi.org/10.1079/bjn19970201>

Chris J Bates challenged the validity of the meta-analysis on vitamin C and susceptibility to colds (1997), and this was response to Bates’ arguments.

Dr Bates makes five specific criticisms of my recent paper (Hemilä, 1997a) to which I shall respond separately...

After his specific criticisms, Bates offered some general opinions on nutritional recommendations. He suggested that the effects of micronutrients should be considered primarily in the light of human intervention studies, a viewpoint which I heartily endorse. However, such an approach has not been applied in the official monographs on these issues.

In the British recommendations no mention is made of the vitamin C and common cold link (Department of Health, 1991) although more than sixty intervention studies have been published on the issue (Kleijnen et al. 1989)[see #16]. In fact, one of the studies cited in the UK recommendations reported that the geometric mean duration of colds was 6.4 days in vitamin C-deprived subjects and 3.3 days in non-deprived subjects, and the authors concluded that the absence of vitamin C tended to cause colds to last longer (Bartley et al. 1953) [see #96, #100]. The brief comment on the vitamin C and plasma cholesterol relationship is based on one single uncontrolled study (Department of Health, 1991)²⁶ although over thirty intervention studies have been published, eleven of which were placebo-controlled (Hemilä, 1992b)²⁷.

26 Dietary reference values for food energy and nutrients for the United Kingdom.

Report of the Panel on Dietary Reference Values of the Committee on Medical Aspects of Food Policy. *Rep Health Soc Subj (Lond)*. 1991; p.117-122.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1961974>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13946536>

27 Hemilä H. Vitamin C and plasma cholesterol. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr*. 1992;32(1):33-57.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1290584>

<https://doi.org/10.1080/10408399209527579>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/321504>

8. Hemilä H. **Vitamin C supplementation and the common cold – was Linus Pauling right or wrong?**

Int J Vitam Nutr Res. 1997;67(5):329-35.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9350474>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6406111>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/223748>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/13877876>

... with respect to specific conclusions as to the size of the effect, Pauling was grossly over-enthusiastic. Pauling based his estimates of the benefit on a trial published in 1961, carried out by Ritzel with schoolboys in a skiing camp in the Swiss Alps... Pauling put great weight on it and extrapolated the findings to the general population. He modeled the dose-dependency of the effects of vitamin C supplementation with exponential formulas in which constants were based on Ritzel's data. Pauling assumed that the main problem in his estimates was the inaccuracy caused by the "experimental error," although he also noted that "the values are, of course, expected to depend somewhat on the nature of the population and environment". However, even with these prudent reservations Pauling's conclusions were all too optimistic. He could not imagine how great the variations in the results would be in the forthcoming trials. Neither did Pauling consider the possibility that the effects observed by Ritzel were caused, at least in part, by low dietary vitamin C intake, in which case a smaller dose could have produced a similar benefit. Pauling attributed the difference between the study groups solely to the large dose given to the treatment group... Retrospectively it seems surprising that Pauling did not point out the shortcomings in **Chalmers' review** [see #4, #17] or the flaws in the interpretation of **Karlowski's trial** [see #5, #6, #19]. Pauling did write two papers in which he pointed out certain shortcomings of the **Dykes and Meier review** [see #15]. However, there are important flaws in Dykes and Meier's review that were not pointed out by Pauling.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4941984>

Pauling L. The significance of the evidence about ascorbic acid and the common cold.

Proc Natl Acad Sci USA. 1971

7. Hemilä H. **Vitamin C supplementation and common cold symptoms:**

Problems with inaccurate reviews. Nutrition. 1996;12(11-12):804-9.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/8974108>

<https://zenodo.org/records/18377079>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10250/7979>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/14233989>

[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0899-9007\(96\)00223-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0899-9007(96)00223-7)

See also #4, #14, #15, #17.

widespread conviction that the vitamin has no proven effects on the common cold still remains. Three of the most influential reviews drawing this conclusion are considered in the present article. Two of them are cited in the current edition of the RDA nutritional recommendations as evidence that vitamin C is ineffective against colds.²⁸ In this article, these three reviews are shown to contain serious inaccuracies and shortcomings, making them unreliable sources on the topic.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1089817>

Dykes MH, Meier P. Ascorbic acid and the common cold.

Evaluation of its efficacy and toxicity. JAMA. 1975

28 **US RDA. Recommended Dietary Allowances 1989**

<https://doi.org/10.17226/1349>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK234924>

"Several reviewers (**Chalmers, 1975; Dykes and Meier, 1975**) have concluded that any benefits of large doses of ascorbic acid for these conditions are too small to justify recommending routine intake of large amounts by the entire population." p.120.

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM198609113151113>

Truswell AS. Ascorbic Acid [letter]. N Engl J Med 1986

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1092164>

Chalmers TC. Effects of ascorbic acid on the common cold. An evaluation of the evidence. Am J Med. 1975

6. Hemilä H. **To the dissent by Thomas Chalmers.** J Clin Epidemiol. 1996;49(10):1087.

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225873>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10250/8079>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/28363121>

[https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356\(96\)00191-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356(96)00191-6)

This responds to Thomas Chalmers' critique of #5.

Chalmers comments that "Hemilä accuses us of assuming that if the volunteers guessed correctly which group they were in that means that they knew, which is obviously not the case." ... the JAMA paper itself suggests that the correct answers on the questionnaire were interpreted by the authors as actual knowledge of the treatment, although a great proportion of the correct answers could have been due to correct guesses, as pointed out in my paper.

Chalmers claims that no conclusions on the dose-response relationship can be drawn from their study. This statement seems inconsistent with the JAMA paper, in which the authors commented that "volunteers taking placebo had colds of a mean duration of 7.14 days, while those taking 3 gm of ascorbic acid had colds of a mean duration of 6.59 days and those taking 6 gm had colds of a mean duration of 5.92 days. Thus, each 3-gm increment of ascorbic acid would appear to shorten the mean duration of a cold by approximately half a day."

Thomas Chalmers' (1996) critique of #5 is available at:

[https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356\(96\)00190-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356(96)00190-4)

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/28363121>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225873>

5. Hemilä H. **Vitamin C, the placebo effect, and the common cold: A case study of how preconceptions influence the analysis of results.** J Clin Epidemiol. 1996;49(10):1079-84.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/8826986>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/14378347>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10250/8082>

[https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356\(96\)00189-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356(96)00189-8)

See discussion in #6, and a summary in #19.

As to the importance of Karlowski trial, see #22, #41, #95 and lists in the footnote.²⁹

*One of the most influential common cold studies, published in 1975, was carried out by **Thomas Karlowski et al.** at the National Institutes of Health... The most important conclusions from Karlowski's study are that therapeutic vitamin C supplementation during a common cold episode appears to be as effective as regular supplementation, and that there appears to be linear dose dependency at least up to 6 g/day. These findings suggest that large therapeutic vitamin C doses might alleviate the symptoms of the common cold substantially...*

... there is a problem with the division of subjects into the two categories of "blinded" and "unblinded" as it was done by Karlowski et al. These two groups contained 144 (= 92 + 52) cold episodes (Table 4), whereas there were 249 episodes among all subjects (Table 1). Thus there is a group of missing

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- 29 **Selected list of papers that cite the Karlowski (1975) trial**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20204507>

See also Tables 1 and 2 in:

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35054455>

A Google Scholar search identified 363 citations to the Karlowski (1975) trial by 2026-5.

persons with a total of 105 cold episodes (Table 5); in other words, nearly half of all observed episodes are missing from Karlowski's subgroup analysis [i.e. 42% = 105/249]... It is not clear what Karlowski's explanation for the missing group was, and why it was not shown along with the data for the two other subgroups.³⁰

Etc.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/163386>

Karlowski TR, Chalmers TC, Frenkel LD, Kapikian AZ, Lewis TL, Lynch JM.

Ascorbic acid for the common cold. A prophylactic and therapeutic trial. JAMA. 1975

4. Hemilä H, Herman ZS. **Vitamin C and the common cold: A retrospective analysis of Chalmers' review.**³¹ J Am Coll Nutr. 1995;14(2):116-23.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/7790685>

<https://zenodo.org/records/18376955>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/42358>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/15407891>

<https://doi.org/10.1080/07315724.1995.10718483>

See a summary in #17, see also #35 and #43, and footnote 21.

*In 1975 Thomas Chalmers analyzed the possible effect of vitamin C on the common cold by calculating the average difference in the duration of cold episodes in vitamin C and control groups in seven placebo-controlled studies. He found that **episodes were 0.11 ± 0.24 (SE) days shorter** in the vitamin C groups and concluded that there was no valid evidence to indicate that vitamin C is beneficial in the treatment of the common cold...*

Chalmers did not consider the amount of vitamin C used in the studies and included in his meta-analysis was a study in which only 0.025-0.05 g/day of vitamin C was administered to the test subjects. For some studies Chalmers used values that are inconsistent with the original published results. Using data from the same studies, we calculated that vitamin C (1-6 g/day) decreased the duration of the cold episodes by 0.93 ± 0.22 (SE) days; the relative decrease in the episode duration was 21%.

The current notion that vitamin C has no effect on the common cold seems to be based in large part on a faulty review written two decades ago.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1092164>

Chalmers TC. Effects of ascorbic acid on the common cold. An evaluation of the evidence.

Am J Med. 1975

3. Hemilä H. **Vitamin C and illness.** Skeptical Inquirer 1995;19(Nr.4;July/August):62.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20374293>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225885>

<https://skepticalinquirer.org/1995/07/letters-to-the-editor-143>

Recently Stephen Barrett³² claimed that vitamin C supplementation at best only slightly affects the symptoms of the common cold (SI, January-February)...

30 Some further statistical issues of the Karlowski trial (see #13):

Hemilä H. Analysis of clinical data with breached blindness. Stat Med 2006;25:1434-7.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.2347>

<https://helda.helsinki.fi/handle/10138/228098>

31 **The Chalmers review has been extensively cited in journal articles and textbooks, see Table 3 in:**

<https://doi.org/10.3390/life12010062>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc8779885>

32 **Stephen Barrett, psychiatrist.**

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stephen_Barrett

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quackwatch>

<https://quackwatch.org>

<https://asatonline.org/research-treatment/interviews/interview-with-dr-stephen-barrett-quackwatch-founder>

Barretts claim that at best there is only a slight reduction in symptoms appears grossly misleading considering the published results...

Edgar Villchur commented Barrett's response to Hemilä's criticism (1995;November/December:61-2):

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225885>

<https://skepticalinquirer.org/1995/11/letters-to-the-editor-145>

Barrett's reply in the same issue to the letter challenges Hemilä's reporting accuracy, but Hemilä is correct... Barrett, however, doesn't say he is citing a different part of the Anderson data, and thus makes it seem that Hemilä has either misread or misrepresented Anderson.

Stephen Barrett replied to Villchur's criticism as follows:

Villchur is correct that Hemilä and I referred to different figures.

Thus, apparently Barrett intended to mislead the readers that Hemilä had presented wrong numbers.

<https://skepticalinquirer.org/1995/01/the-dark-side-of-linus-paulings-legacy>

<https://quackwatch.org/related/pauling>

Barrett S. The dark side of Linus Pauling's legacy.

Skeptical Inquirer 1995;19(Nr.1;Jan/Feb).

2. Hemilä H. **The good and harm of vitamin C.** Nutrition Today 1994;29:49-50.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/00017285-199403000-00008>

https://journals.lww.com/nutritiontodayonline/citation/1994/03000/the_good_and_harm_of_vitamin_c.8

<https://hdl.handle.net/10250/135155>

Victor Herbert³³ recently discussed the beneficial and harmful aspects of vitamin C supplementation. In his brief discussion of the possible benefits, he neglected to mention the effect of vitamin C on the common cold. Over 20 placebo-controlled studies have consistently shown that vitamin C (1-6 g/day) alleviates the symptoms of the common cold...

Herbert presented a list of other possible harms from vitamin C supplementation (1). He did not explicitly refer to the original publications, but took the list from another review (13). The list contains the claim, originally made by Herbert himself, that vitamin C causes breakdown of vitamin B12 (14). However, it was shown over ten years ago that the reported decrease in vitamin B₁₂ level was due to methodological shortcomings (15,16), and the vitamin B₁₂ level is not decreased in patients that have been given as much as 4 g/day of vitamin C (17).

Herbert also claims that vitamin C may cause miscarriages (1,13). This suggestion is based on a brief Russian publication from 27 years ago (18).³⁴ Twenty women whose menstruation was delayed by 10-15 days were given 6 g/day of vitamin C, and 16 of them started to menstruate within 3 days (18). Pauling wrote a letter to the authors inquiring whether any direct test of pregnancy was carried out, but as a reply he received only a copy of the publication (7). Thus, there is no evidence that the women were pregnant initially; possibly they just had irregular menstruation.

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- 33 **Victor Herbert, hematologist.**

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Victor_Herbert_\(hematologist\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Victor_Herbert_(hematologist))

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(03\)12336-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(03)12336-7)

<https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/77.4.757>

<https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/134.7.1678>

<https://doi.org/10.1002/ajh.10306>

<https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/26.9.907>

- 34 Samborskaya EP, Ferdman TD. The mechanism of termination of pregnancy by ascorbic acid.

Bulletin of Experimental Biology and Medicine 1966;62:934-5.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00810734>

English summary in the Chemical Abstracts: AN 1966:493662.

<https://zenodo.org/records/19892392>

Five decades ago Levey and Suter reported that vitamin C potentiates the diabetogenic action of alloxan in rats (19).³⁵ Blood sugar level was determined 3 days after injecting alloxan, or alloxan with vitamin C (0.2 g/kg), to the rats. Hyperglycemia was observed in 50% of the rats treated with alloxan and vitamin C, in contrast to 17% of the rats treated with alloxan alone (19). The authors concluded from their own previous work that “ascorbic acid alone does not produce hyperglycemia” (19). This old experiment with alloxan-treated rats is the basis for Herbert’s belief that large doses of vitamin C, alone, may reduce insulin production in human subjects (1,13)...

Thus, Herbert’s conclusions that there are no reliable data to show that vitamin C supplementation may provide any benefits, and that vitamin C supplements may instead be highly harmful, are largely based on biased selection of references.

https://journals.lww.com/nutritiontodayonline/abstract/1993/01000/viewpoint_does_mega_c_do_more_good_than_harm_or_7

Victor Herbert. Viewpoint: Does mega-C do more good than harm, or more harm than good?

Nutrition Today 28(1):p 28-32, January 1993

1. Hemilä H. **Vitamin C, cholesterol, and the nutritional recommendations.**

Am J Cardiol. 1993;71(5):503-4.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/8430669>

[https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9149\(93\)90498-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9149(93)90498-2)

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225880>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/14767979>

A short critique on the US RDA (1989) recommendations:

The effect of vitamin C on plasma cholesterol has been extensively studied, but only 2 intervention studies are mentioned in the RDA monograph... Moreover, neither of the 2 studies had a placebo group. A decrease in elevated cholesterol levels as a result of vitamin C supplementation has also been found in 3 placebo-controlled studies, although none of these studies is mentioned in the RDA monograph... The RDA recommendations may be highly useful for specific purposes such as setting a minimal standard of nutrition in order to prevent overt deficiencies in institutions, etc. Nevertheless, more attention should be given to the findings that the recommended levels are not optimal for sickness prevention or therapy, and that in certain cases much larger doses may be beneficial.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25144070> US RDA. Recommended Dietary Allowances 1989.

<https://doi.org/10.17226/1349>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK234924>

<https://www.nationalacademies.org/publications/1349>

National Research Council (US) Subcommittee on the Tenth Edition of the Recommended Dietary Allowances.

Recommended Dietary Allowances: 10th Edition.

Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US); 1989.

“Large doses of ascorbic acid have also been reported to lower serum cholesterol in some hypercholesterolemic subjects (Ginter et al., 1977), but these observations have not been confirmed by others (Peterson et al., 1975)” p.120-1.

35 Levey S, Suter B. Effect of ascorbic acid on diabetogenic action of alloxan.

Proc Soc Exp Biol Med. 1946;63(2):341-3.

<https://zenodo.org/records/19892132>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20277744>

<https://doi.org/10.3181/00379727-63-15595>